

Research paper

Novel tacrine-based multi-target directed Ligands: Enhancing cholinesterase inhibition, NMDA receptor antagonism, and CNS bioavailability for Alzheimer's disease treatment

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Tacrine
Acetylcholinesterase
Butyrylcholinesterase
N-methyl-D-aspartate receptor
Multi-target directed ligands
Alzheimer's disease

ABSTRACT

Alzheimer's disease (AD) is a multifaceted neurodegenerative disorder for which current treatments provide only symptomatic relief, primarily through cholinesterase (ChE) inhibition and N-methyl-D-aspartate receptor (NMDAR) antagonism. To improve therapeutic efficacy and safety, we designed and synthesized 16 novel tacrine derivatives modified at position 7 with various (hetero)aryl groups or deuterium substitution. Initially, *in silico* screening predicted favorable CNS permeability and oral bioavailability. Subsequent *in vitro* evaluations demonstrated significant inhibitory potency against acetylcholinesterase (AChE) and butyrylcholinesterase (BChE), with derivatives **5i** and **5m** displaying particularly promising profiles. Metabolic stability assessed using human liver microsomes revealed enhanced stability for compound **5e**, whereas **5i** and **5m** underwent rapid metabolism. Notably, compound **7** showed improved metabolic stability attributed to deuterium incorporation. The newly synthesized compounds were further tested for antagonistic activity on the GluN1/GluN2B subtype of NMDAR, with compound **5m** exhibiting the most potent and voltage-independent inhibition. The ability of these compounds to permeate the blood-brain barrier (BBB) was confirmed through *in vitro* PAMPA assays. In preliminary hepatotoxicity screening (HepG2 cells), most derivatives exhibited higher cytotoxicity than tacrine, emphasizing the ongoing challenge in hepatotoxicity management. Based on its overall favorable profile, compound **5m** advanced to *in vivo* pharmacokinetic studies in mice, demonstrating efficient CNS penetration, with brain concentrations exceeding plasma levels (brain-to-plasma ratio 2.36), indicating active transport across the BBB. These findings highlight compound **5m** as a promising tacrine-based multi-target-directed ligand, supporting further preclinical development as a potential therapeutic candidate for AD.

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejmech.2025.117678>

Received 5 March 2025; Received in revised form 8 April 2025; Accepted 22 April 2025

Available online 22 April 2025

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1. Introduction

Alzheimer's disease (AD) is a progressive neurodegenerative disorder characterized by a gradual decline, ultimately leading to death [1]. It involves the steady deterioration of neuronal function, resulting in cognitive and behavioral impairments. These changes are usually accompanied by apathy, irritability, anxiety, and depression [2]. Predominantly affecting the elderly, AD imposes a considerable burden on global healthcare systems and represents a significant socioeconomic challenge. As reported by the World Health Organization (WHO), more than 55 million people worldwide are living with dementia, with AD accounting for 60–70 % of these cases. With the continued aging of the global population, this number is projected to increase to 139 million by 2050 [3].

Immense efforts have been made so far in the elucidation of underlying AD pathomechanisms [4,5]. The decreased level of acetylcholine (ACh) in the CNS is one of the most pronounced characteristics of AD [6, 7]. Other major AD hallmarks, such as extracellular formation and accumulation of amyloid- β (A β) and intracellular neurofibrillary tangles (NFT), have an interconnection with cholinergic system malfunction [8, 9]. Furthermore, oxidative stress, neuroinflammation, and biometal dyshomeostasis are also critical contributors to the multifaceted pathogenesis of AD [10–12]. These mechanisms have become primary targets in developing potential therapeutics. Except for the recently approved monoclonal antibodies, no effective or curative treatments have been discovered [13,14].

The current therapeutic approach for AD remains primarily symptomatic, focusing on acetylcholinesterase inhibitors (AChEIs) such as donepezil, galantamine, and rivastigmine, alongside the *N*-methyl-D-aspartate receptor (NMDAR) antagonist memantine [15]. These treatments are often complemented with adjunct therapies, including antidepressants, anxiolytics, and antipsychotics (with a few examples shown in Fig. 1) [16–19]. Recently, the therapeutic field has expanded with the accelerated approval of disease-modifying agents by the Food and Drug Administration (FDA), namely lecanemab (2023) and donanemab (2024) [20,21]. These monoclonal antibodies, which target amyloid-beta (A β) aggregation, have demonstrated modest benefits by slowing cognitive decline in the early stages of AD [22–24]. However, their global approval is currently restricted, as further clinical evidence is required to fully assess their efficacy [20].

Given the multifactorial and complex nature of AD, polypharmacology has emerged as a viable therapeutic strategy with clinical applications. Namzaric®, a combination of donepezil and memantine,

was approved by the FDA in 2014 [25]; however, its marketing authorization was denied by the European Medicines Agency (EMA). Combination therapies, especially those involving antibodies, present significant challenges due to their complexity, high costs, and specialized healthcare professionals' requirement for intravenous administration [26]. In contrast, the polypharmacological approach based on multi-target-directed ligands (MTDLs)—single small molecules capable of modulating multiple targets within the AD pathological network—offers a more promising strategy [27]. MTDLs demonstrate advantages in terms of efficacy, reduced toxicity, and lower overall costs [25].

Tacrine (THA; 1,2,3,4-tetrahydro-9-aminoacridine) was the first FDA-approved drug for the treatment of AD. Its primary mechanism involves the inhibition of acetylcholinesterase (AChE; E.C. 3.1.1.7), indirectly stimulating the cholinergic system. However, its mode of action is more intricate, encompassing interactions with additional targets, including NMDARs, muscarinic, nicotinic receptors, and others [28,29]. Although its clinical use was discontinued in 2013 due to hepatotoxicity [30,31], the THA scaffold remains a pivotal pharmacophore in medicinal chemistry [32,33].

In this study, we aimed to design novel and less hepatotoxic THA-derived MTDLs to target dysfunctions in both the cholinergic and glutamatergic systems. In designing these novel THA-based MTDLs, we employed a rational approach guided by structural and metabolic considerations to optimize inhibitory potency towards AChE while also reducing hepatotoxicity inherent in the THA scaffold. Substitutions at position 7 were carefully selected based on known SAR, aiming to enhance metabolic stability and CNS bioavailability. For instance, incorporating heteroaryl groups such as pyridine, pyrimidine, furan, and thiophene was chosen due to their known resistance to enzymatic cleavage compared to oxygen-linked substituents, thus potentially reducing toxic metabolite formation [34]. Additionally, deuterium substitution was considered to exploit the kinetic isotope effect, theoretically shifting metabolism away from toxic metabolites [35]. Regarding NMDAR antagonism, compounds were designed considering previous findings that THA-based scaffolds interact with the ifenprodil-binding site of GluN1/GluN2B receptors [36]. To this end, we synthesized 16 THA derivatives and evaluated their inhibitory potency against cholinesterases (ChEs), specifically AChE and butyrylcholinesterase (BChE; EC 3.1.1.8). In addition, chromatographic techniques were employed to examine specific physico-chemical characteristics, including lipophilicity, the binding of drugs to plasma proteins, and affinity for phospholipids. Furthermore, we have screened the

Fig. 1. Chemical structures of currently approved drugs for treating AD and selected adjunct therapeutics.

compounds for their ability to cross the blood-brain barrier (BBB) and assessed their potential cytotoxicity on the human hepatocyte carcinoma (HepG2) cell line. Based on the results, we identified the most promising candidates and further examined their microsomal stability, effects on NMDAR antagonism, dehydrogenase activity, and glutathione levels. Following a down-selection process, compound **5m** emerged as the lead candidate and progressed to an *in vivo* pharmacokinetic (PK) study.

2. Results and discussion

2.1. Design of novel compounds combining ChE and NMDAR affinities

As previously mentioned, the primary challenge associated with the drug discovery of THA-based compounds lies in the hepatotoxicity of the parent molecule. To address this issue, we have recently developed several derivatives [37,38], including 7-phenoxytacrine (7-PhO-THA) (Fig. 2) [39,40]. This compound combines dual inhibitory effects on AChE and NMDARs with favorable pharmacological properties. It selectively inhibits GluN1/GluN2B receptors via the ifenprodil-binding site and exhibits voltage-dependent inhibition of both GluN1/GluN2A and GluN1/GluN2B subunits. Furthermore, 7-PhO-THA demonstrates neuroprotective efficacy *in vivo* without causing behavioral side effects typical for NMDAR antagonists. A key advantage of 7-PhO-THA and its derivatives lies in the substitution of position 7 of the basic THA scaffold, which prevents the formation of metabolites such as 7-hydroxytacrine (7-OH-THA) and its quinone methide derivative. These undesirable products are major contributors to the hepatotoxicity of THA. However, not all modifications at position 7 led to similar results. For instance, 7-MEOTA, designed to avoid liver biotransformation, still produces 7-OH-THA during metabolism, highlighting the complexity of addressing THA-related toxicity [41,42].

Herein, in the design of novel potential drugs for AD, we extended our attention to agents, which are attached directly to the primary THA structure (Fig. 2). We introduce alternative groups, including aromatic heterocycles or aromatic rings at position 7, as C–C bonds are known to be more resistant to enzymatic cleavage, leading to increased metabolic stability of drugs [43,44]. In contrast, C–O bonds are more susceptible to

hydrolysis and oxidation by metabolic enzymes, potentially leading to rapid drug degradation and elimination [45]. In addition to (hetero)aryl substitution, we also explored the incorporation of deuterium, a bioisostere of hydrogen, at the same position. The C–D bond is stronger than the C–H bond due to the kinetic isotope effect, which can modify the metabolic pathway or reduce the hydroxylation rate. This alteration can decrease the formation of toxic metabolites, thereby enhancing the compound's safety profile [46–48].

All the newly designed compounds were initially screened *in silico* to predict their peroral and/or CNS availabilities. These properties are crucial considerations in the drug discovery process for potential anti-AD therapeutics and should be assessed prior to synthesis. For this purpose, the *in silico* pharmacokinetics, drug-likeness, and ADME (absorption, distribution, metabolism, excretion) prediction was applied to compounds **5a–5o** and **7**. These data are presented in Tables S1–S3, Figs. S1 and S2. (Supplementary Information; SI).

2.2. Chemical synthesis of novel 7-(aryl)heteroaryl-THA derivatives **5a–5o**, and 7-[²H]-THA hydrochloride **7**

All the newly designed compounds were synthesized as outlined in Scheme 1. Compounds **5a–5o** were prepared in two-step chemical synthesis according to the previously described methods [37,49]. The initial step involved the Friedländer condensation of 2-amino-5-bromobenzonitrile **1** in the presence of cyclohexanone **2** and Lewis acid (ZnCl₂), affording 7-bromotacrine formation (**3**). The reaction proceeded under microwave-assisted conditions. Finally, the palladium-catalyzed cross-coupling reactions between the appropriately substituted arylboronic acids **4a–4o** and **3** were carried out in the mixture of THF/H₂O, resulting in compounds **5a–5o** in good overall yields (11–64%). Compound **7** was prepared in one-step chemical synthesis, where intermediate **3** reacted with deuterium gas in deuterated methanol and triethylamine. The reaction mixture was catalyzed by 10% Pd/C. All the final compounds were characterized by ¹H and ¹³C NMR, HRMS, and LC-UV analysis confirmed their purity to be higher than 95%. Deuterium enrichment (>0.97 atom D per molecule) was determined from the mass spectrum (all spectra are available at Supporting Information).

Fig. 2. Rational design of novel 7-THA derivatives combining ChE and NMDAR antagonism.

Scheme 1. General procedure for 7-hetero(aryl)-THA derivatives **5a–5o**, and 7- ^{2}H -Tacrine hydrochloride **7**. Reagents and conditions: i) ZnCl_2 (2.0 eq.); cyclohexanone (5 mL); Mw; 5 min; $160\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, ii) **4a–4o** (1.2 eq.); Na_2CO_3 (2.0 eq.); bis(triphenylphosphine)palladium(II) chloride (0.1 eq.); THF/ H_2O (4:1); 24 h; $75\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, iii) 10 % Pd/C; D_2 ; Et_3N (1.5 eq.); $\text{MeOD-}d_4$ (2 mL), iv) EtOH (10 mL); HCl.

2.3. Lipophilicity, drug-plasma proteins binding, and phospholipids affinity assays

Following the *in silico* approach, which demonstrated promising characteristics of the designed structures, the subsequent phase involves experimental verification of the most critical properties. To assess these parameters, we utilized the biomimetic chromatography platform developed by Valko at GlaxoSmithKline, which allows for measuring of acid-base properties, lipophilicity, and binding to phospholipids and plasma proteins in a cost-effective and time-saving manner [50–52]. In Table 1, the obtained chrom $\log D_{7.4}$, phospholipophilicity index (CHI_{IAM}), Property Forecast Index (PFI), and %HSA have been collected.

Lipophilicity is crucial in drug absorption, distribution, metabolism, excretion, and toxicity (ADMET), influencing membrane permeability, protein binding, and metabolic stability. The results showed that most of the investigated derivatives exhibited moderate lipophilicity, a little higher compared to the parent structure of THA. Furthermore, when

Table 1
Chromatographically determines properties of tested molecules and PFI.

Compound	CHI IAM	Chrom $\log D$ at $\text{pH}_{2.6}$	Chrom $\log D$ at $\text{pH}_{7.4}$	Chrom $\log D$ at $\text{pH}_{10.5}$	PFI	% HSA
5a	20.2	0.47	3.52	3.05	6.5	91.4
5b	25.3	1.63	3.69	3.99	6.7	94.3
5c	26.0	1.60	3.65	4.15	6.6	94.3
5d	23.0	1.44	3.24	3.81	6.2	90.2
5e	14.7	0.99	2.73	2.59	5.7	72.1
5f	19.1	1.26	2.94	3.20	5.9	85.2
5g	12.2	0.65	1.20	1.40	4.2	73.9
5h	26.2	1.59	3.43	4.08	6.4	94.7
5i	29.5	1.94	4.06	4.58	7.1	95.5
5j	29.9	1.78	3.80	4.48	6.8	97.1
5k	29.6	1.77	3.85	4.54	6.9	96.8
5l	37.9	2.28	4.86	5.42	7.9	99.2
5m	33.0	2.12	4.41	4.96	7.4	97.8
5n	31.6	1.40	4.50	4.86	7.5	96.2
5o	38.8	2.87	5.58	5.79	8.6	99.3
7	14.4	0.71	2.31	2.99	4.3	56.5
THA	14.4	0.71	2.31	2.99	4.3	56.5
7-PhO-THA	27.6	1.83	3.82	4.49	6.8	92.9

comparing the chromatographic $\log D_{7.4}$ value for the non-ionized form of THA with the data available in the literature [53], a high degree of agreement can be seen, 2.99 vs. 2.71, respectively. Adequate lipophilicity also translates into adequate PFI, an index used at GSK to assess developability issues, where a value of less than seven is preferred. Similarly, the target molecules demonstrated a moderate affinity for phospholipids. The lipophilic nature of a molecule is widely recognized as a crucial factor in governing its affinity towards phospholipids, so the high correlation between CHI_{IAM} and chromatographic $\log D_{7.4}$ is in line with expectations ($r = 0.96$). Determining chromatographic $\log D$ values across a range of acid-base conditions facilitates the interpretation of the acid-base nature of the tested compounds. The observed decrease in chromatographic $\log D_{7.4}$ values under acidic conditions indicates that all the investigated compounds possess a weak basicity center.

This study utilized chromatographic columns with surface modifications containing HSA, the predominant plasma protein, to estimate drug-HSA binding. Such protein-binding interactions influence key pharmacokinetic parameters, including drug distribution, elimination half-life, and clearance. In the case of our group, their basic nature will make HSA the main plasma protein responsible for their binding. Therefore, results with %HSA for THA remain consistent with the literature %PPB, 56 % vs. 55 % [54]. In the case of the newly synthesized derivatives, a significant increase in binding to HSA is observed. This can partly be explained by the lipophilicity pattern, with high correlations between chromatographic $\log D_{7.4}$ and $\log k_{\text{HSA}}$ ($r = 0.84$). Nevertheless, maintaining an acceptable level of HSA binding remains critical in drug discovery [55].

2.4. Evaluation of cholinesterase inhibitory activity

AChE inhibition remains pivotal to AD symptomatic therapy. As the disease progresses, AChE levels decline, whereas BChE levels remain stable or may slightly increase as a compensatory mechanism to counteract the loss of neuronal AChE activity [56,57]. For these reasons, we have established the inhibition activity against both human AChE (hAChE) and human BChE (hBChE). The modified spectrophotometric method of Ellman et al. [58–60] was applied to assess the inhibitory potency of the novel compounds. THA and 7-PhO-THA were used as

reference compounds. The IC_{50} values of all tested derivatives and their selectivity index (SI) for hAChE are summarized in Table 2.

All compounds effectively inhibited both types of ChEs at the micromolar range. The IC_{50} values ranged from 0.160 μ M (**5i**) to 1.179 μ M (**5a**) and 0.059 μ M (**7**) to 2.475 μ M (**5g**) for hAChE and hBChE, respectively. The derivatives of THA substituted with pyridine (**5a–5d**) displayed a non-selective inhibition pattern. Among these, compound **5c**, bearing 6-chloropyridine at position 7 of the THA scaffold, demonstrated the highest inhibitory potency. In contrast, compound **5a**, containing an unsubstituted pyridine, exhibited the weakest activity within this group. In the pyrimidine series (**5e–5g**), structural variations on the pyrimidine core had a negligible impact on inhibitory potency. This was exemplified by derivative **5e** endowed with unsubstituted pyrimidine, which exhibited the highest level of BChE inhibition within the subset. For compounds containing a furan moiety (**5h–5i**), substitution with a methyl group on the furan ring significantly enhanced potency. Indeed, compound **5i** was ten times more effective against AChE and twice as potent against BChE than **5h**. Notably, derivative **5i** emerged as the most effective AChE inhibitor (hAChE IC_{50} = 0.160 μ M) among the entire (hetero)aryl-THA series. Similarly, substitution with a thiophene group at position 7 of the THA scaffold produced derivatives **5j–5m**, with **5m** exhibiting the strongest inhibition against both enzymes. In fact, compound **5m** was the most effective BChE inhibitor (hBChE IC_{50} = 0.165 μ M) within the (hetero)aryl-THA series. The aryl-THA derivatives **5n** and **5o** exhibited comparable IC_{50} values, similar to those of **5k** and **5b**. Overall, substitution with a five-membered heteroaryl ring generally led to more potent inhibition than substituting with a six-membered ring. The deuterated THA analogue **7** displayed inhibitory activity closely resembling that of THA, as expected, given the minimal structural modification. Nonetheless, compound **7** emerged as the most potent BChE inhibitor (hBChE IC_{50} = 0.059 μ M) among all the newly synthesized derivatives. All compounds, except for **5i** and **7**, exhibited lower inhibitory activity relative to THA. Nevertheless, all newly developed derivatives showed markedly greater inhibitory potency than the reference molecule 7-PhO-THA.

Lipophilic ligand efficiency (LLE) is a parameter that integrates both potency and lipophilicity, serving as a measure of how effectively a ligand utilizes its lipophilicity to bind to a specific target [61]. In the context of lead optimization, compounds are more likely to exhibit favorable *in vivo* performance if their potency can be enhanced without

Table 2
The inhibitory activities of compounds **5a–5o** and **7** for hAChE and hBChE.

Compound	hAChE $IC_{50} \pm SEM$ (μ M) ^a	hBChE $IC_{50} \pm SEM$ (μ M) ^a	SI ^b
5a	1.179 \pm 0.097	1.857 \pm 0.748	1.58
5b	0.677 \pm 0.032	0.614 \pm 0.023	0.91
5c	0.287 \pm 0.016	0.343 \pm 0.023	1.20
5d	0.900 \pm 0.033	0.857 \pm 0.063	0.95
5e	0.985 \pm 0.036	0.857 \pm 0.063	0.87
5f	0.603 \pm 0.034	1.956 \pm 0.106	3.24
5g	0.914 \pm 0.070	2.475 \pm 0.173	2.71
5h	1.646 \pm 0.136	1.171 \pm 0.074	0.71
5i	0.160 \pm 0.009	0.563 \pm 0.020	3.25
5j	0.444 \pm 0.015	0.205 \pm 0.003	0.46
5k	0.948 \pm 0.065	0.521 \pm 0.014	0.55
5l	0.370 \pm 0.013	0.207 \pm 0.003	0.56
5m	0.334 \pm 0.008	0.165 \pm 0.004	0.49
5n	0.948 \pm 0.026	0.487 \pm 0.003	0.51
5o	0.625 \pm 0.050	0.653 \pm 0.040	1.04
7	0.198 \pm 0.006	0.059 \pm 0.001	0.30
THA	0.222 \pm 0.004	0.056 \pm 0.010	0.25
7-PhO-THA	4.421 \pm 0.099	3.252 \pm 3.300	0.74

^a Results are expressed as the mean of at least three experiments.

^b SI = selectivity index, selectivity for hAChE is determined as ratio $IC_{50}(hBChE)/IC_{50}(hAChE)$; SEM = standard error of mean.

increasing their $\log P$ or $\log D$ values. While $\log P$ is commonly used to describe lipophilicity, it does not account for the ionization of functional groups at varying pH values, making it less reliable in biologically relevant conditions. In contrast, $\log D$ offers a more comprehensive view by considering ionization. Potency can be assessed through early-stage biochemical assays or more functionally relevant cell-based assays (equation (1)) [62–64].

$$LLE (\text{LipE}) = -\log (K_i \text{ or } IC_{50}) - \log D (\text{ or } \log P) \quad (1)$$

To investigate this concept further, we calculated LLE values for the entire set of substituted THA derivatives and the reference standards. The $\log D_{7.4}$ values vary from 1.20 to 5.58 (Table 1), leading to an LLE range between 0.61 and 4.94 (Table S4). It is well-established that an LLE value greater than 5, combined with $\log D$ values between 1.5 and 3, is optimal for a promising drug candidate [65,66]. By analyzing the data in an LLE plot format (Fig. 3) instead of a potency-only format, we immediately identified the compounds worthy of further optimization because they have the highest LLE rather than just the best potency. Unfortunately, none of those derivatives, including standards, have reached the required LLE threshold. However, the deuterated analogue of THA **7** (LLE (AChE) = 4.39; LLE (BChE) = 4.92) and compound **5g** (LLE (AChE) = 4.84; LLE (BChE) = 4.41) were very close to achieving this benchmark.

2.5. Prediction of BBB permeability

To confirm the *in silico*-predicted ability of all compounds to penetrate through the BBB, the parallel artificial membrane permeability assay (PAMPA) was used [67,68]. The assay validation has been performed using standard compounds whose CNS status is experimentally known from *in vivo* conditions [69–71]. The results of commercial drugs and new investigational compounds are summarized in Table 3. Based on the results, most compounds demonstrated a high probability of crossing BBB via passive diffusion. The derivative **5o** exhibited the most favorable outcome. However, permeability predictions for compounds **5h**, **5i**, **5j**, and **5m** remain uncertain as these compounds reached permeability values that lie between assay positive and negative outcomes.

2.6. In vitro hepatotoxicity assay

It is well-known that the hepatotoxicity of THA and its derivatives is a critical issue that needs to be addressed in the early stage of drug discovery. The MTT (3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide) colorimetric assay performed on human hepatocellular carcinoma (HepG2) cell line was applied to investigate the preliminary hepatotoxicity profile of all the developed derivatives [72]. The results are summarized in Table 4. The IC_{50} values of the synthesized compounds ranged from 2.71 to 120.3 μ M. Among the compounds, the deuterated analogue of THA (**7**) exhibited the lowest cytotoxicity, followed by derivatives substituted with pyridine and pyrimidine of the THA scaffold, specifically **5a** and **5e**. However, all synthesized compounds demonstrated higher cytotoxicity than the reference compound THA.

This data must be considered carefully since MTT cytotoxicity screening is performed on isolated cell lines. Thus, these results provide only a preliminary hepatotoxicity insight and do not reflect the toxicity profile under *in vivo* conditions.

2.7. In vitro drug metabolism stability

Determining the metabolic profiles of new chemical structures is a fundamental step in drug discovery, as it significantly impacts the pharmacokinetic properties and overall therapeutic potential of compounds [73]. Chemical entities can generally be divided into those that

Fig. 3. Correlation of ChEs inhibitory potency vs. $\log D$ values of compounds **5a–5o**, **7**, and standards. Color denotes improving LLE from dark green to light green. $pIC_{50} = -\log(IC_{50} \text{ AChE or BChE})$. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Table 3

Prediction of the blood-brain barrier penetration of studied compounds **5a–5o**, and **7** expressed as $Pe \pm SEM$.

Compound	$Pe \pm SEM (\times 10^{-6} \text{ cm s}^{-1})^1$	CNS predicted availability ²	Compound	$Pe \pm SEM (\times 10^{-6} \text{ cm s}^{-1})^1$	CNS predicted availability ²
5a	5.62 ± 1.43	+	5m	3.99 ± 2.05	+/-
5b	9.96 ± 1.31	+	5n	4.50 ± 0.72	+
5c	8.75 ± 0.15	+	5o	16.2 ± 1.88	+
5d	5.00 ± 1.42	+	7	7.39 ± 1.09	+
5e	7.20 ± 0.64	+	THA	5.90 ± 0.67	+
5f	7.98 ± 0.96	+	Donepezil	21.9 ± 2.06	+
5g	8.81 ± 1.14	+	Rivastigmine	18.7 ± 2.03	+
5h	3.45 ± 0.32	+/-	Ibuprofen	18.0 ± 4.32	+
5i	3.09 ± 0.13	+/-	Chlorothiazide	1.14 ± 0.54	-
5j	3.54 ± 0.59	+/-	Furosemide	0.19 ± 0.07	-
5k	5.31 ± 1.35	+	Ranitidine	0.04 ± 0.02	-
5l	6.99 ± 1.81	+	Sulfasalazine	0.09 ± 0.05	-

¹Novel compounds were measured $n = 2-4$, the reference compounds were measured $n = 2-8$; ² + (high BBB permeation predicted): $Pe (\times 10^{-6} \text{ cm s}^{-1}) > 4.0$; - (low BBB permeation predicted): $Pe (\times 10^{-6} \text{ cm s}^{-1}) < 2.0$; +/- (BBB permeation uncertain): $Pe (\times 10^{-6} \text{ cm s}^{-1})$ from 4.0 to 2.0 [67].

undergo rapid metabolism and those that exhibit slow biotransformation. Rapid metabolism reduces the exposure of the parent compound, often resulting in the formation inactive, or even toxic metabolites. In contrast, high metabolic stability can increase the risk of drug-drug interactions and may lead to toxicity caused by the accumulation of the parent compound [74].

Metabolic stability is commonly expressed through *in vitro* half-life ($t_{1/2}$) and intrinsic clearance (CL_{int}). The $t_{1/2}$ represents the time required for 50 % of the parent compound to degrade, while CL_{int}

reflects the maximum metabolic activity of liver enzymes (microsomal proteins or hepatocytes) on the tested compound. Unlike $t_{1/2}$, CL_{int} is not influenced by physiological factors such as hepatic blood flow or plasma protein binding *in vitro* [75–77].

From the previous results, we selected five derivatives, namely **5a**, **5e**, **5i**, **5m**, and **7**, to evaluate human liver microsomal (HLM) stability. These candidates were chosen based on several criteria: (i) the highest inhibition of AChE (**5i**), BChE (**7** and **5m**); (ii) the highest LLE values (**7**); (iii) and the lowest cytotoxicity (**5a**, **5e**, and **7**). Despite its high LLE

Table 4

Cytotoxicity of tested compounds on the human origin cell lines HepG2 expressed as IC₅₀ ± SEM.

Compound	IC ₅₀ ± SEM (μM) ^a	Compound	IC ₅₀ ± SEM (μM) ^a
5a	15.19 ± 0.64	5i	6.65 ± 0.01
5b	7.41 ± 0.36	5j	7.40 ± 0.24
5c	3.83 ± 0.24	5k	7.08 ± 0.45
5d	3.19 ± 0.11	5l	4.52 ± 0.27
5e	26.54 ± 0.41	5m	6.19 ± 0.26
5f	5.31 ± 0.41	5n	6.92 ± 0.19
5g	3.42 ± 0.40	5o	2.71 ± 0.22
5h	7.83 ± 0.49	7	120.3 ± 3.5
THA	168.5 ± 3.6	7-PhO-THA	22.33 ± 0.05

^a Data were obtained from at least four independent experiments performed in triplicates.

value, compound **5g** was excluded from further testing due to the structural liability. It is well-documented that the methoxy group is metabolically unstable, particularly in (hetero)aryl methyl ethers, where the primary metabolic pathway involves *O*-demethylation, often followed by glucuronidation [78].

THA, 7-MEOTA, diazepam, 7-PhO-THA, and verapamil were used as reference compounds for comparison. Diazepam and verapamil represent drugs with low and high metabolic turnover, respectively [79]. The HLM stability of these standards after 45 min of incubation was compared with the selected lead candidates (Table 5). Consistent with literature data, verapamil exhibited experimentally high intrinsic clearance (CL_{int} = 90.09 μL/min/mg) and a short half-life (t_{1/2} = 15.40 min). At the same time, diazepam showed low metabolic clearance (CL_{int} = 4.60 μL/min/mg) and an extended half-life (t_{1/2} = 301.30 min) [40]. In addition to the metabolic stability of the tested compound, the amount of formed 7-OH-THA metabolite was also monitored, as it is a precursor of hepatotoxic quinone methide derivative [41].

Among the THA derivatives, compounds **5i** and **5m** exhibited high CL_{int} and low t_{1/2} values, meaning that these compounds are rapidly metabolized, and their bioavailability *in vitro* will probably be low. The potential hepatotoxic effects of compound **5i** can be attributed to furan ring oxidation as multiple hydroxylation of the compound was determined (data not shown). Depending on the substituents on the furan ring, the intermediate is either an epoxide or a *cis*-enedione [73,80]. Since the 2-position of the furan ring is blocked by a methyl group and the 5-position is occupied by the THA scaffold, epoxide formation is less likely, while the formation of a *cis*-enedione is more probable. For derivative **5m**, the thiophene ring will likely to undergo P450-catalyzed hydroxylation at the carbon atoms adjacent to the sulfur atom, forming of 2-hydroxythiophene. However, from the obtained, the oxidation site can only be speculated. According to the literature, it is also possible

Table 5

Determination of microsomal stability (represented by HLM half-life (t_{1/2}), intrinsic clearance (CL_{int})) and the amount of formed 7-OH-THA (expressed by area and related percentage to THA in %) from selected compounds, including standards.

Compound	HLM t _{1/2} (min)	CL _{int} (μL/min/mg protein)	Area of 7-OH-THA formed
5a	30.00	46.25	172.8 E+6 (49 %)
5e	93.65	14.81	200.7 E+6 (57 %)
5i	5.80	239.04	215.5 E+6 (61 %)
5m	6.20	223.62	207.0 E+6 (59 %)
7	110.00	12.61	337.0 E+6 (96 %)
THA	108.28	12.81	351.0 E+6 (100 %)
7-MEOTA	330.00	4.20	473.1 E+6 (135 %)
7-PhO-THA	32.84	42.24	13.2 E+6 (0.04 %)
Diazepam	301.30	4.60	N.D.
Verapamil	15.40	90.09	N.D.

N.D. stands for not detected.

that the thiophene can be oxidized to unstable and reactive thiophene-S-oxide metabolites [81].

Six-membered heteroaryl groups are often used to replace aryl moiety to improve a drug's physical properties and metabolic stability. However, these heteroaryl cores remain susceptible to metabolism at either the carbon atoms or the heteroatoms [82]. Compound **5a**, featuring a pyridine ring, showed moderate CL_{int} and t_{1/2}, similar to 7-PhO-THA. On the other hand, compound **5e**, which contains a pyrimidine ring, demonstrated higher microsomal stability (t_{1/2} = 93.65 min) similar to THA (t_{1/2} = 108.28 min), indicating lower metabolic turnover by liver enzymes and improved stability against enzymatic degradation. Collectively, these results suggest that adding an extra nitrogen atom to the ring reduces its metabolic susceptibility by lowering the LogD_{7.4} (Table 1) and decreasing the susceptibility to interact with the CYP450 system [81]. Generally, for all four tested compounds (**5a**, **5e**, **5i**, **5m**), the amount of formed 7-OH-THA was reduced to 49–61 % in comparison to THA, which means that THA (hetero)aryl substituted derivatives could partially prevent from the formation of toxic quinone methide.

In the case of compound **7**, we initially hypothesized that incorporating deuterium into the THA core would enhance its metabolic stability [83]. However, the results indicate that the t_{1/2} and CL_{int} values of compound **7** are nearly identical to THA. Similarly, the formation of 7-OH-THA from compound **7** occurred at comparable levels to THA (Table 5). A detailed HRMS spectral analysis further revealed the presence of deuterated 7-OH-THA, confirming that deuterium-labeled metabolites were formed. Overall, these outcomes can be attributed to a phenomenon known as metabolic switching (NIH shift), which is the metabolic process in which deuterium migrates to some of the close carbon atoms. Therefore, the deuteration at one site can redirect metabolism to alternative pathways and increase activity at other sites [35].

2.8. Evaluation of antagonist activity towards NMDAR

Next, we investigated the effects of the top-ranked candidates, i.e., **5a**, **5e**, **5i**, and **5m**, on interaction with a specific subtype of NMDAR associated with neurodegeneration, namely the GluN1/GluN2B receptor [84]. The rationale for testing the compounds for their affinity toward NMDAR is based on the well-established interaction of THA-based compounds with these receptors [37,40,85]. Compound **7** was excluded from this evaluation due to its similarity to THA. We tested the derivatives by the whole-cell patch-clamp method at a concentration of 10 μM under steady-state conditions at membrane potentials of −60 or +40 mV in the presence of the saturating concentrations of NMDAR (co-agonists L-glutamate and glycine). Our measurements showed that all tested derivatives exhibited inhibition toward the GluN1/GluN2B receptor, ranging from ~61 to ~88 % at membrane potential −60 mV and ~20–~88 % at membrane potential +40 mV (Table 6). The compound **5e** exhibited a voltage-dependent effect similar to that observed for 7-MEOTA. In contrast, compounds **5a**, **5i**, and **5m** displayed voltage-independent inhibitory effects, suggesting their interaction with the ifenprodil-binding site of the GluN1/GluN2B receptor, akin to 7-PhO-THA. The involvement of this site is further supported by previous findings with 7-PhO-THA, which exhibited voltage-dependent inhibition of GluN1/GluN2A receptors—lacking the ifenprodil site—but voltage-independent inhibition of GluN1/GluN2B receptors. This pattern is consistent with selective binding to the ifenprodil site [39,40]. Notably, the inhibitory potency of compounds **5i** and **5m** was comparable to 7-PhO-THA at both −60 mV and +40 mV and memantine at −60 mV. Concentration-response curve analysis of the most potent compound, **5m**, revealed an IC₅₀ value of 2.12 ± 0.23 μM with a Hill coefficient of 1.52 ± 0.13 at a membrane potential of −60 mV (n = 5; Fig. 4), highlighting the promising potency of these new derivatives at NMDARs.

Table 6

Relative inhibition (RI, %) of selected and reference compounds against GluN1/GluN2B NMDAR.

Compound (10 μ M)	RI \pm SEM, % (-60 mV)	n	RI \pm SEM, % (+40 mV)	n
5a	60.14 \pm 1.73	9	56.07 \pm 2.80	7
5e	61.22 \pm 3.10	10	19.95 \pm 1.17	8
5i	85.18 \pm 1.94	10	88.19 \pm 3.14	8
5m	87.11 \pm 2.23	8	86.95 \pm 1.65	7
7-PhO-THA	88.25 \pm 1.35	7	84.97 \pm 2.73	7
7-MEOTA	59.98 \pm 2.04	6	20.66 \pm 1.11	8
Memantine	94.63 \pm 1.07	5	24.86 \pm 1.67	7

Relative inhibition (RI, % \pm SEM) of selected compounds at GluN1/GluN2B NMDARs measured at the steady-state conditions at membrane potentials of -60 or +40 mV, where n equals the number of analyzed cells.

2.9. Assessment of dehydrogenase activity and glutathione levels in neuronal cells

To evaluate the neurotoxicity of selected derivatives **5i**, **5m**, THA, and 7-PhO-THA *in vitro*, we tested the cytotoxic effects of the compounds in SH-SY5Y cells. The SH-SY5Y cell line was used because it is frequently associated with neurotoxicity evaluation [86–88]. We tested the biological effects of **5i**, **5m**, THA, and 7-PhO-THA (0–100 μ M) at three different time points: 6, 24 and 48 h (Table 7). To evaluate the effects of a compound in cells, we measured intracellular dehydrogenase activity as a marker of cellular viability, glutathione (GSH) levels to estimate oxidative stress, and ATP level as a marker of the energy state of cells.

According to the findings from dehydrogenase activity, GSH, and ATP measurements, **5i** and **5m** caused the most profound cell impairment. In SH-SY5Y cells treated with both 25 and 100 μ M **5i** and **5m**, we found significant decreases in dehydrogenase activity ($p < 0.001$), GSH ($p < 0.001$), and ATP ($p < 0.001$) levels after 24 and 48 h of treatment compared to untreated cells. These results are supported by photomicrographs of SH-SY5Y cells treated with 25 μ M **5i** and 25 μ M **5m**, showing a large extent of cell damage (Fig. 5) where SH-SY5Y cells exhibit spherical shape and cell density lower than in untreated cells.

In SH-SY5Y cells exposed to THA, we detected significant decreases in dehydrogenase activity ($p < 0.001$) and ATP levels ($p < 0.001$) only in cells treated with the highest concentration of 100 μ M THA after 48 h, compared to controls. After the treatment with 100 μ M 7-PhO-THA, the significant impairment of SH-SY5Y cells progressed between 6 and 48 h of incubation according to the measurements of dehydrogenase activity, GSH, and ATP levels. However, the extent of cellular damage was lower than in the cases of **5i** and **5m**. We did not detect any morphological changes in SH-SY5Y cells after incubation with 25 μ M THA and 25 μ M 7-PhO-THA of 24 h.

2.10. In vivo pharmacokinetic study of compound 5m

Based on the *in vitro* data obtained, compound **5m** was selected for the *in vivo* analysis. Pharmacokinetic experiments were conducted in

male BALB/c mice. No signs of toxicity were observed at either dose (10 mg/kg and 15 mg/kg). Therefore, the 15 mg/kg dose was identified as the no observed adverse effect level (NOAEL). This dose was used in the pharmacokinetic study, and no signs of toxicity were observed again. The macroscopic examination revealed no abnormalities in the intraperitoneal cavity (administration site), kidneys, or liver. These findings were consistent with histopathological observations, where all renal samples (including controls) exhibited increased glomerular epithelial thickness, indicative of the young age of the experimental animals. Similarly, in the liver, anisocytosis and residual hematopoiesis were observed. No other pathological changes were detected. Following intraperitoneal (i.p.) administration, the compound **5m** was successfully detected in the plasma and brain (Fig. 6). The experimental data were analyzed using standard non-compartmental analysis in PKanalix (v. 2024R1), and the results are summarized in Table 8. Compound **5m** exhibited simple pharmacokinetics, with a single peak in both plasma and brain. The compound was actively transported across the BBB, with a brain-to-plasma ratio (calculated from AUC_{0-120}) of 2.36. Such value suggests the involvement of an active influx transport mechanism at the BBB. Typically, passive diffusion alone would result in similar brain and plasma concentrations ($K_p \approx 1$), whereas higher concentrations in brain tissue strongly imply active transport processes facilitating CNS penetration.

3. Conclusion

Developing therapeutics that effectively address multiple pathological targets simultaneously remains crucial due to the complexity of AD. In the current study, we rationally designed and synthesized novel THA-based MTDLs by modifying the THA scaffold at position 7 with various (hetero)aryl substituents and deuterium substitution. These modifications aimed at enhancing ChE inhibitory potency, reducing hepatotoxicity, and introducing antagonistic activity against NMDA receptors, specifically at the GluN1/GluN2B subunit, implicated in AD pathophysiology. Our comprehensive evaluation, including computational predictions, detailed *in vitro* enzyme assays, receptor pharmacology, metabolic stability tests, and preliminary hepatotoxicity assessments, led to the identification of compounds with improved pharmacological profiles. Notably, derivative **5m** emerged as a lead candidate demonstrating promising cholinesterase inhibition, potent and voltage-independent NMDA receptor antagonism, and favorable blood-brain barrier permeability, confirmed by pharmacokinetic studies in mice. This compound exemplifies the potential and feasibility of the MTDL strategy for AD therapy. However, limitations identified, such as rapid metabolic clearance and increased cytotoxicity for certain derivatives, emphasize the necessity for further optimization to balance potency, safety, and metabolic properties. Specifically, *in vitro* cytotoxicity assessments indicated that some derivatives, notably **5i** and **5m**, exhibit significant neurotoxic and hepatotoxic effects, reinforcing the need for structural optimization to minimize toxicity and ensure safety alongside efficacy. Overall, this work provides valuable insights and novel

Fig. 4. (A) Typical response from a HEK293 cell transfected with GluN1/GluN2B receptors, triggered by the co-application of 1 mM glutamate (Glu) and 100 μ M glycine (Gly). The inhibitory activity of **5m** was measured at a membrane potential of -60 mV, with the final concentrations of compound **5m** indicated (0.1–30 μ M). (B) The concentration-inhibition curve for compound **5m** was constructed by fitting the experimental data using Equation (1).

Table 7

Biochemical changes in SH-SY5Y cells treated with (0–100 μM) **5i**, **5m**, THA, and 7-PhO-THA for 6, 24, and 48 h. After treatment, dehydrogenase activity using the resazurin assay, glutathione levels using the monochlorobimane assay, and ATP level using the luciferase luminescence assay were measured.

	c (μM)	GSH level (% of control)			Dehydrogenase activity (% of control)			ATP level (% of control)		
		6 h	24 h	48 h	6 h	24 h	48 h	6 h	24 h	48 h
5i	0	100 \pm 12	100 \pm 5	100 \pm 4	100 \pm 4	100 \pm 2	100 \pm 2	100 \pm 3	100 \pm 3	100 \pm 4
	1	109 \pm 11	105 \pm 4	102 \pm 9	104 \pm 3	107 \pm 6	103 \pm 5	98 \pm 4	106 \pm 2	98 \pm 7
	10	113 \pm 16	122 \pm 7***	117 \pm 13	90 \pm 11	96 \pm 6	82 \pm 7***	91 \pm 7	87 \pm 9	90 \pm 7
	25	99 \pm 15	40 \pm 6***	0 \pm 0***	66 \pm 1***	6 \pm 0***	0 \pm 0***	51 \pm 1***	4 \pm 1***	3 \pm 1***
	100	0 \pm 0***	0 \pm 0***	0 \pm 0***	12 \pm 5***	0 \pm 0***	0 \pm 0***	11 \pm 3***	1 \pm 1***	1 \pm 1***
5m	1	108 \pm 10	99 \pm 6	98 \pm 7	108 \pm 4	108 \pm 7	106 \pm 4	95 \pm 9	108 \pm 3	102 \pm 6
	10	97 \pm 10	99 \pm 10	95 \pm 11	95 \pm 10	114 \pm 6	87 \pm 14*	87 \pm 11	111 \pm 4	95 \pm 8
	25	95 \pm 3	27 \pm 4***	6 \pm 4***	68 \pm 2***	5 \pm 0***	0 \pm 0***	50 \pm 1***	3 \pm 0***	2 \pm 0***
	100	35 \pm 7***	7 \pm 7***	4 \pm 6***	4 \pm 2***	0 \pm 0***	0 \pm 0***	3 \pm 1***	1 \pm 1***	0 \pm 1***
	THA	1	98 \pm 12	97 \pm 9	95 \pm 3	98 \pm 4	98 \pm 5	103 \pm 6	98 \pm 7	97 \pm 2
7-PhO-THA	10	104 \pm 15	93 \pm 7	93 \pm 3	96 \pm 5	98 \pm 3	100 \pm 6	100 \pm 13	91 \pm 6	91 \pm 6
	25	86 \pm 5	98 \pm 5	90 \pm 4	95 \pm 2	98 \pm 6	90 \pm 1	100 \pm 6	87 \pm 16	97 \pm 5
	100	93 \pm 8	106 \pm 10	101 \pm 4	93 \pm 3	90 \pm 9	77 \pm 6***	93 \pm 5	93 \pm 5	82 \pm 8**
7-PhO-THA	1	114 \pm 13	107 \pm 6	106 \pm 5	97 \pm 3	102 \pm 9	98 \pm 3	111 \pm 13	102 \pm 4	104 \pm 14
	10	99 \pm 13	107 \pm 10	90 \pm 7	96 \pm 8	104 \pm 8	97 \pm 3	91 \pm 18	91 \pm 8	90 \pm 9
	25	92 \pm 11	93 \pm 7	76 \pm 3***	103 \pm 6	121 \pm 5**	93 \pm 3	74 \pm 4***	86 \pm 0	78 \pm 3**
	100	94 \pm 11	36 \pm 9***	12 \pm 8***	79 \pm 8***	61 \pm 5***	23 \pm 1***	31 \pm 8***	16 \pm 10***	4 \pm 4***

The data are presented as mean \pm SEM (n = 3–6; three independent experiments). Statistical significance was analyzed using ANOVA followed by Tukey's test to compare results with negative controls at significance level $p = 0.05$ (*, $p < 0.05$; **, $p < 0.01$; ***, $p < 0.001$, vs. untreated cells at appropriate time interval).

chemical entities that contribute to advancing the field of multi-target therapeutics for neurodegenerative diseases, particularly AD.

4. Materials and methods

4.1. General methods and chemistry for compounds **3**, **5a–5o**

All chemical solvents and reagents were used in the highest available purity without further purification, and they were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Prague, Czech Republic); FluoroChem (Hadfield, United Kingdom) or BLDpharm (Shanghai, China). The reactions were monitored by thin layer chromatography (TLC) on silica gel plates (60 F254, Merck, Prague, Czech Republic) and the spots were visualized by ultraviolet light (254 nm). Purification of crude products were carried out using columns of silica gel (silica gel 100, 0.063–0.200 mm, 70–230 mesh ASTM, Fluka, Prague, Czech Republic) and PuriFlash GEN5 column, 5.250 (Interchim, Montluçon, France) (silica gel 100, 60 \AA , 230–400 mesh ASTM, Sigma-Aldrich, Prague, Czech Republic). NMR spectra were recorded in deuterated chloroform (CDCl_3), deuterated methanol (CD_3OD), and deuterated dimethyl sulfoxide ($\text{DMSO}-d_6$) on Bruker Avance NEO 500 MHz spectrometer (499.87 MHz for ^1H NMR, and 125.71 MHz for ^{13}C NMR). Chemical shifts (δ) are reported in parts per million (ppm) and spin multiplicities are given as broad singlet (bs), doublet (d), doublet of doublet (dd), triplet (t), quartet (q), pentet (p), or multiplet (m). Coupling constants (J) are reported in Hz. The synthesized compounds were analyzed by the LC-MS system consisting of UHPLC Dionex Ultimate 3000 RS with a diode array detector coupled with Q Exactive Plus mass spectrometer to obtain UV purity and high-resolution mass spectra (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Bremen, Germany). Melting points were measured using an automated melting point recorder M – 565 (Büchi, Switzerland). Gradient LC analysis confirmed >95 % purity.

4.1.1. Preparation of compound **3**

Commercially available starting material **1** (1.0 eq.) and **2** (5 mL) were charged into a microwave tube. ZnCl_2 (2.0 eq.) was added to the reaction mixture. The reaction mixture proceeded under microwave conditions (100 W, 300 psi, 160 $^\circ\text{C}$) for 5 min. After completion of the reaction (observed by TLC), the reaction mixture was extracted between 2 M NaOH (100 mL) and DCM (3 \times 100 mL). The organic phases were combined, dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 , and filtered. The filtrate was concentrated under reduced pressure, and the reaction mixture was

purified by flash chromatography using DCM/MeOH/25 % aqueous NH_3 (20:1:0.1) as the mobile phase. Compound **3** was obtained as a free base with a 92 % yield.

4.1.1.1. (bromo)-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroacridin-9-amine (3). Yield: 92 %. White crystalline powder; melting point: > 255 $^\circ\text{C}$. ^1H NMR (500 MHz, Methanol- d_4): δ 8.27 (t, $J = 1.4$ Hz, 1H), 7.61 (d, $J = 1.6$ Hz, 2H), 2.90 (t, $J = 6.1$ Hz, 2H), 2.60 (t, $J = 6.2$ Hz, 2H), 1.97–1.87 (m, 4H) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, Methanol- d_4): δ 158.00, 148.63, 144.31, 131.55, 128.13, 123.80, 118.21, 116.29, 110.02, 32.71, 23.29, 22.36, 22.33 ppm; HRMS: $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$ calculated for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{14}\text{BrN}_2$: 277.0335; found: 277.0334. LC-UV purity 99 %.

4.1.2. General procedure for the preparation of compounds **5a–5o**

Intermediate **3** (1.0 eq.), commercially available arylboronic acids **4a–4o** (1.2 eq.), Na_2CO_3 (2.0 eq.), and bis(triphenylphosphine)palladium (II) chloride (0.1 eq.) were weighed into a 100 mL flask. THF/ H_2O (4:1) were then added to the flask. The reaction mixture was carried out under the argon atmosphere at 75 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 24 h. After completion of the reaction (observed by TLC), the reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature and then extracted between 2 M NaOH (100 mL) and EA (3 \times 100 mL). The organic phases were combined, dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 , and filtered. The filtrate was concentrated under reduced pressure, and the reaction mixture was purified by flash chromatography using DCM/MeOH/25 % aqueous NH_3 (9:1:0.1) as the mobile phase. Compounds **5a–5o** were obtained as free bases or hydrochloride salts (12–70 % yields).

4.1.2.1. 7-(pyridin-4-yl)-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroacridin-9-amine hydrochloride (5a). Yield: 70 %. Yellow crystalline powder; melting point: 196–197 $^\circ\text{C}$. ^1H NMR (500 MHz, $\text{DMSO}-d_6$): δ ^1H NMR (500 MHz, $\text{DMSO}-d_6$) δ 14.14 (s, 1H), 9.48 (bs, 1H), 9.35 (d, $J = 2.0$ Hz, 1H), 9.02–8.98 (m, 2H), 8.53 (d, $J = 6.0$ Hz, 2H), 8.50 (dd, $J = 9.0, 1.9$ Hz, 1H), 8.37 (bs, 1H), 8.10 (d, $J = 8.9$ Hz, 1H), 3.02 (t, 2H), 2.58 (t, 2H), 1.93–1.82 (m, 4H). ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, $\text{DMSO}-d_6$): δ 156.40, 152.68, 144.62, 138.73, 131.80, 131.73, 124.47, 123.72, 120.73, 115.46, 110.57, 104.77, 99.53, 76.25, 28.31, 23.09, 21.42, 20.91 ppm; HRMS: $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$ calculated for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_3$: 276.1496; found: 276.1488. LC-UV purity 97 %.

4.1.2.2. 7-(2-methoxy-pyridin-4-yl)-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroacridin-9-amine (5b). Yield: 41 %. White crystalline powder; melting point: 182–183 $^\circ\text{C}$.

Fig. 5. Visualization of SH-SY5Y cells treated with 25 μM concentration of **5i**, **5m**, THA, and 7-PhO-THA for 24 h. Shown photomicrographs were selected as representatives of the performed experiments. Phase contrast (left column); actin filaments (phalloidin-FITC; middle column); cells nuclei (Hoechst 33258; right column).

^1H NMR (500 MHz, $\text{DMSO}-d_6$): δ 8.60 (dd, $J = 2.6, 0.7$ Hz, 1H), 8.40 (d, $J = 2.1$ Hz, 1H), 8.12 (dd, $J = 8.6, 2.6$ Hz, 1H), 7.77 (dd, $J = 8.7, 2.0$ Hz, 1H), 7.63 (d, $J = 8.7$ Hz, 1H), 6.88 (d, $J = 8.5$ Hz, 1H), 3.85 (s, 3H), 2.77 (t, $J = 6.1$ Hz, 2H), 2.51 (t, $J = 6.2$ Hz, 2H), 1.81–1.69 (m, 4H) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, $\text{DMSO}-d_6$): δ 163.32, 157.97, 148.83, 146.07, 145.20, 138.00, 131.45, 129.69, 129.08, 126.74, 119.47, 117.67, 110.94, 109.74, 53.72, 34.00, 24.18, 23.10, 22.99 ppm; HRMS: $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$ calculated for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_3\text{O}^+$: 306.1601; found: 306.1593. LC-UV purity 99 %.

4.1.2.3. 7-(6-chloropyridin-3-yl)-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroacridin-9-amine hydrochloride (5c). Yield: 32 %. Yellowish crystalline powder; melting point: 181–182 $^\circ\text{C}$. ^1H NMR (500 MHz, $\text{DMSO}-d_6$): δ 13.98 (s, 1H), 9.14 (bs, 1H), 8.97 (dd, $J = 6.0, 2.3$ Hz, 2H), 8.40 (dd, $J = 8.4, 2.7$ Hz, 1H), 8.29 (dd, $J = 8.9, 1.9$ Hz, 1H), 8.20 (bs, 1H), 8.01 (d, $J = 8.8$ Hz, 1H), 7.71 (d, $J = 8.4$ Hz, 1H), 3.00 (t, 2H), 2.57 (t, $J = 5.9$ Hz, 2H), 1.91–1.81 (m, 5H) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, $\text{DMSO}-d_6$): δ 155.96, 151.98, 150.32, 148.54, 138.33, 137.27, 133.74, 132.91, 131.62, 124.94, 121.88, 120.41, 115.51, 110.02, 28.24, 23.07, 21.46, 20.96 ppm; HRMS: $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$ calculated for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{17}\text{ClN}_3$: 310.1106; found: 310.1097. LC-UV purity 95 %.

Fig. 6. Plasma and brain profiles following a single administration (i.p., 15 mg/kg) in male Balb/c mice (n = 4). The results are expressed as mean \pm SEM.

Table 8

Pharmacokinetic parameters in plasma and brain following a single administration (i.p., 15 mg/kg) in male Balb/c mice.

5 m	PLASMA	BRAIN
C_{max} (nM)	944.71 \pm 144.20	1467.08 \pm 230.06
T_{max} (min)	15.00 \pm 0.00	26.25 \pm 7.50
AUC_{0-120} (nM \times min)	46 523 \pm 16 845	109 960 \pm 19 106
AUC_i (nM \times min)	64 556 \pm 22 774	117 646 \pm 23 315
KP1-120 brain (AUC_{brain}/AUC_{plasma})		2.36

C_{max} , maximal plasma or brain concentration; T_{max} , time to C_{max} ; AUC_{0-120} , area under curve 0–120 min/bioavailability; AUC_i , area under curve (infinity)/bioavailability; Kp, Brain-to-Plasma Partition Coefficient. All values are expressed as mean \pm SEM of four independent measurements.

4.1.2.4. 7-(6-fluoropyridin-3-yl)-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroacridin-9-amine hydrochloride (5d). Yield: 49 %. Yellow crystalline powder; melting point: 152–153 °C. 1H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ 14.09 (s, 1H), 9.14 (bs, 1H), 8.93 (t, J = 2.0 Hz, 1H), 8.78 (d, J = 2.7 Hz, 1H), 8.53 (ddd, J = 8.7, 7.8, 2.7 Hz, 1H), 8.24 (dd, J = 8.9, 1.8 Hz, 1H), 8.17 (bs, 1H), 8.01 (d, J = 8.8 Hz, 1H), 7.37 (dd, J = 8.6, 2.8 Hz, 1H), 3.01 (t, J = 6.1 Hz, 2H), 2.54 (t, 2H), 1.91–1.81 (m, 4H) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, DMSO): δ 163.31 (d, J = 236.8 Hz), 155.87, 151.80, 146.29 (d, J = 15.4 Hz), 140.99 (d, J = 8.0 Hz), 137.07, 133.06, 132.91 (d, J = 4.4 Hz), 131.54, 121.62, 120.30, 115.47, 110.24 (d, J = 37.7 Hz), 109.86, 28.20, 23.06, 21.47, 20.95 ppm; HRMS: $[M+H]^+$ calculated for $C_{18}H_{17}FN_3^+$: 294.1402; found: 294.1402. LC-UV purity 97 %.

4.1.2.5. 7-(pyrimidin-5-yl)-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroacridin-9-amine hydrochloride (5e). Yield: 28 %. White crystalline powder; melting point: 214–215 °C. 1H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ 14.15 (bs, 1H), 9.39 (s, 2H), 9.24 (s, 1H), 9.06 (d, J = 2.0 Hz, 1H), 8.33 (dd, J = 8.8, 1.9 Hz, 1H), 8.04 (d, J = 8.8 Hz, 1H), 3.00 (t, J = 5.6 Hz, 2H), 2.54 (t, J = 5.8 Hz, 2H), 1.90–1.81 (m, 4H) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ 158.00, 155.91, 155.39, 152.06, 137.46, 132.08, 131.28, 130.96, 122.17, 120.47, 115.50, 110.03, 56.48, 28.22, 23.06, 21.45, 20.93 ppm; HRMS: $[M+H]^+$ calculated for $C_{17}H_{17}N_4^+$: 277.1448; found: 277.1440. LC-UV purity 95 %.

4.1.2.6. 7-(2-methoxypyrimidin-5-yl)-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroacridin-9-amine (5f). Yield: 24 %. Yellowish crystalline powder; melting point: 263–265 °C. 1H NMR (500 MHz, Methanol- d_4): δ 8.95 (s, 2H), 8.33–8.29 (m, 1H), 7.84–7.79 (m, 2H), 4.07 (s, 3H), 2.93 (t, J = 6.1 Hz, 2H), 2.63 (t, J = 6.3 Hz, 2H), 1.98–1.87 (m, 4H) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, Methanol- d_4): δ 164.57, 158.09, 157.19, 149.63, 145.41, 128.84, 128.13, 127.45, 126.57, 118.97, 117.18, 109.83, 54.25, 48.45, 32.79, 23.34, 22.45, 22.41 ppm; HRMS: $[M+H]^+$ calculated for $C_{18}H_{19}N_4O^+$: 307.1554; found: 307.1548. LC-UV purity 95 %. (March 15, 2023).

4.1.2.7. 7-(2,4-dimethoxypyrimidin-5-yl)-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroacridin-9-amine (5g). Yield: 28 %. Brown crystalline powder; melting point: 90–91 °C. 1H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ 8.48 (s, 1H), 8.27 (d, J = 1.9 Hz, 1H), 7.70–7.62 (m, 2H), 3.97 (s, 3H), 3.96 (s, 3H), 2.84 (t, J = 6.0 Hz, 2H), 2.56 (t, J = 6.1 Hz, 2H), 1.88–1.74 (m, 4H) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ 168.16, 164.45, 158.47, 158.13, 148.71, 146.06, 129.33, 128.08, 127.77, 122.16, 117.37, 116.17, 109.66, 55.05, 54.49, 34.03, 24.15, 23.10, 23.00 ppm; HRMS: $[M+H]^+$ calculated for $C_{19}H_{21}N_4O_2^+$: 337.1660; found: 337.1650. LC-UV purity 99 %.

4.1.2.8. 7-(furan-3-yl)-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroacridin-9-amine hydrochloride (5h). Yield: 30 %. Yellowish crystalline powder; melting point: 130–132 °C. 1H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ 13.82 (bs, 1H), 8.81 (d, J = 1.8 Hz, 1H), 8.40 (dd, J = 1.5, 0.9 Hz, 1H), 8.14 (dd, J = 8.8, 1.8 Hz, 1H), 7.89 (d, J = 8.8 Hz, 1H), 7.83 (t, J = 1.7 Hz, 1H), 7.25 (dd, J = 1.9, 0.9 Hz, 1H), 2.98 (t, 2H), 2.55 (t, J = 6.1 Hz, 2H), 1.89–1.79 (m, 5H) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ 155.65, 151.26, 145.19, 140.88, 136.40, 131.04, 129.83, 125.45, 119.97, 119.60, 109.71, 109.19, 56.48, 23.08, 21.51, 21.00, 19.03 ppm; HRMS: $[M+H]^+$ calculated for $C_{17}H_{17}N_2O^+$: 265.1336; found: 265.1328. LC-UV purity 97 %.

4.1.2.9. 7-(5-methylfuran-2-yl)-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroacridin-9-amine hydrochloride (5i). Yield: 39 %. Yellow crystalline powder; melting point: 214–216 °C. 1H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ 14.01 (bs, 1H), 8.77 (d, J = 1.8 Hz, 1H), 8.10 (dd, J = 8.9, 1.7 Hz, 1H), 7.94 (d, J = 8.8 Hz, 1H), 7.09 (d, J = 3.2 Hz, 1H), 6.28 (dd, J = 3.3, 1.2 Hz, 1H), 2.97 (t, J = 5.8 Hz, 2H), 2.54 (t, J = 5.8 Hz, 2H), 2.39 (d, J = 1.1 Hz, 3H), 1.88–1.77 (m, 4H) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ 155.57, 153.13, 151.19, 150.85, 136.30, 128.55, 128.23, 120.16, 116.91, 115.62, 109.73, 109.17, 109.13, 28.15, 23.08, 21.52, 20.98, 19.03, 14.05 ppm; HRMS: $[M+H]^+$ calculated for $C_{18}H_{19}N_2O^+$: 279.1492; found: 279.1484. LC-UV purity 99 %.

4.1.2.10. 7-(thiophen-3-yl)-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroacridin-9-amine hydrochloride (5j). Yield: 44 %. Yellow crystalline powder; melting point: 125–127 °C. 1H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ 13.91 (bs, 1H), 8.91 (d, J = 1.9 Hz, 1H), 8.26 (dd, J = 8.8, 1.8 Hz, 1H), 8.17 (dd, J = 2.9, 1.3 Hz, 1H), 7.93 (d, J = 8.8 Hz, 1H), 7.87 (dd, J = 5.1, 1.4 Hz, 1H), 7.73 (dd, J = 5.0, 2.9 Hz, 1H), 2.97 (t, J = 5.8 Hz, 2H), 2.55 (t, J = 5.9 Hz, 2H), 1.88–1.79 (m, 4H) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ 155.79, 151.30, 140.46, 136.49, 132.67, 131.51, 127.97, 126.86, 122.84, 120.16, 120.03, 115.59, 109.67, 28.17, 23.08, 21.52, 20.99 ppm; HRMS: $[M+H]^+$ calculated for $C_{17}H_{17}N_2S^+$: 281.1107; found: 281.1099. LC-UV purity 99 %.

4.1.2.11. 7-(thiophen-2-yl)-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroacridin-9-amine hydrochloride (5k). Yield: 61 %. Light brown crystalline powder; melting point: 180–182 °C. 1H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ 13.85 (bs, 1H), 8.81 (d, J = 2.0 Hz, 1H), 8.14 (dd, J = 8.8, 1.9 Hz, 1H), 7.93 (d, J = 8.8 Hz, 1H), 7.79 (dd, J = 3.6, 1.2 Hz, 1H), 7.67 (dd, J = 5.0, 1.2 Hz, 1H), 7.22 (dd, J = 5.1, 3.6 Hz, 1H), 2.98 (t, J = 5.8 Hz, 2H), 2.56 (t, J = 5.9 Hz, 2H), 1.90–1.81 (m, 4H) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ 155.71, 151.48, 142.34, 136.66, 131.63, 131.10, 129.20, 127.43, 125.73, 120.43, 119.30, 115.64, 109.94, 28.20, 23.11, 21.50, 20.98 ppm;

HRMS: $[M+H]^+$ calculated for $C_{17}H_{17}N_2S^+$: 281.1107; found: 281.1100. LC-UV purity 99 %.

4.1.2.12. *7-(5-chlorothiophen-2-yl)-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroacridin-9-amine hydrochloride (5l)*. Yield: 12 %. Light brown crystalline powder; melting point: > 285 °C. 1H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ 13.92 (bs, 1H), 8.75 (d, $J = 2.0$ Hz, 1H), 8.07 (dd, $J = 8.8, 1.9$ Hz, 1H), 7.92 (d, $J = 8.9$ Hz, 1H), 7.66 (d, $J = 4.0$ Hz, 1H), 7.24 (d, $J = 4.0$ Hz, 1H), 2.97 (t, $J = 5.8$ Hz, 2H), 2.54 (t, $J = 5.9$ Hz, 2H), 1.89–1.80 (m, 4H) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ 155.68, 151.60, 141.33, 136.86, 130.48, 130.43, 128.95, 128.91, 125.43, 120.50, 119.42, 115.55, 110.04, 28.19, 23.10, 21.47, 20.95 ppm; HRMS: $[M+H]^+$ calculated for $C_{17}H_{16}ClN_2S^+$: 315.0718; found: 315.0708. LC-UV purity 95 %.

4.1.2.13. *7-(4-methylthiophen-2-yl)-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroacridin-9-amine hydrochloride (5m)*. Yield: 31 %. Brown crystalline powder; melting point: 156–158 °C. 1H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ 13.95 (bs, 1H), 8.75 (d, $J = 2.0$ Hz, 1H), 8.07 (dd, $J = 8.8, 1.9$ Hz, 1H), 7.93 (d, $J = 8.8$ Hz, 1H), 7.62 (d, $J = 1.5$ Hz, 1H), 7.23 (t, $J = 1.3$ Hz, 1H), 2.97 (t, $J = 5.9$ Hz, 2H), 2.55 (t, $J = 5.9$ Hz, 2H), 2.27 (d, $J = 1.2$ Hz, 3H), 1.89–1.80 (m, 4H). ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ 155.63, 151.40, 141.94, 139.08, 136.59, 131.70, 130.77, 127.79, 122.52, 120.37, 118.95, 115.61, 109.86, 28.18, 23.10, 21.50, 20.98, 16.03 ppm; HRMS: $[M+H]^+$ calculated for $C_{18}H_{19}N_2S^+$: 295.1264; found: 295.1256. LC-UV purity 98 %.

4.1.2.14. *7-[3-(dimethylamino)phenyl]-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroacridin-9-amine hydrochloride (5n)*. Yield: 48 %. Brown crystalline powder; melting point: 114–116 °C. 1H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ 8.40 (d, $J = 2.0$ Hz, 1H), 7.83 (dd, $J = 8.7, 2.0$ Hz, 1H), 7.69 (d, $J = 8.8$ Hz, 1H), 7.28 (t, $J = 8.1$ Hz, 1H), 7.12–7.05 (m, 2H), 6.73 (dd, $J = 8.2, 2.4$ Hz, 1H), 2.98 (s, 6H), 2.84 (t, $J = 6.0$ Hz, 2H), 2.57 (t, $J = 6.2$ Hz, 2H), 1.87–1.78 (m, 4H) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ 157.56, 151.41, 149.11, 145.84, 141.27, 135.86, 129.79, 128.44, 127.78, 119.83, 117.49, 115.67, 111.91, 111.42, 109.60, 40.80, 33.81, 24.16, 23.05, 22.97 ppm; HRMS: $[M+H]^+$ calculated for $C_{21}H_{24}N_3^+$: 318.1965; found: 318.1957. LC-UV purity 97 %.

4.1.2.15. *7-[3-(2-methylpropoxy)phenyl]-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroacridin-9-amine hydrochloride (5o)*. Yield: 17 %. White crystalline powder; melting point: 79–81 °C. 1H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ 13.96 (bs, 1H), 8.82 (d, $J = 2.0$ Hz, 1H), 8.23 (dd, $J = 8.9, 1.9$ Hz, 1H), 7.99 (d, $J = 8.8$ Hz, 1H), 7.46–7.42 (m, 3H), 7.02–6.99 (m, 1H), 3.87 (d, $J = 6.5$ Hz, 2H), 3.00 (t, 2H), 2.56 (t, 2H), 2.12–2.00 (m, 1H), 1.92–1.79 (m, 4H), 1.02 (d, $J = 6.7$ Hz, 6H) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ 159.93, 155.96, 151.57, 140.22, 137.39, 136.91, 132.15, 130.62, 121.08, 120.09, 119.72, 115.52, 114.46, 113.79, 109.73, 74.38, 56.48, 28.30, 23.12, 21.52, 20.99, 19.61, 19.03 ppm; HRMS: $[M+H]^+$ calculated for $C_{23}H_{27}N_2O^+$: 347.2118; found: 347.2109. LC-UV purity 98 %.

4.2. General chemistry for compound 7

All chemicals were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. Solvents used for the reaction or purification of the product were purchased from Acros Organics, VWR, Penta and Eurisotop in the case of deuterated solvents. Deuteration experiments were performed on a customised stainless deuterium manifold system (RC Triton AG, Teufen, Switzerland) using deuterium gas (99.8 atom% D, Sigma-Aldrich). Flash chromatography was carried out on a CombiFlash® NextGen 300+ instrument (Teledyne ISCO, Lincoln, Nebraska). 1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker Avance II spectrometer at 300 MHz and 75 MHz, respectively, at 25 °C. NMR spectra were calibrated to the signal using the residual non-deuterated solvent (2.50 and 39.52 ppm for DMSO- d_6). LC-MS analyses were performed on the Waters Alliance HPLC system with a Water SQ Detector 2 quadrupole mass detector using ESI ionization mode. HR-MS

spectrum was obtained in the ESI mode on either a Waters-Micromass Q-TOF Micro Mass Spectrometer or a Thermo Fisher Scientific LTQ Orbitrap XLc.

4.2.1. Procedure for the preparation of compound 7

The deuteration flask (6 mL) was charged with intermediate 3 (0.101 mmol, 28 mg), 10 % Pd/C (14 mg), Et₃N (0.151 mmol, 21 μ L, 1.5 eq.), and MeOD- d_4 (2 mL). The flask was connected to a deuteration manifold, and the mixture was degassed three times using the freeze-thaw method. Deuterium gas (390 mbar) was introduced into the reaction flask. The frozen solution was warmed to room temperature (1150 mbar). The reaction was stirred vigorously at room temperature for 6 h. Then, the catalyst was removed by a syringe PTFE filter, and the solvent was evaporated under vacuum. The reaction was repeated six times. All reaction mixtures were mixed, and the crude product was purified by reverse phase flash chromatography (a gradient from 5 % to 60 % of MeCN during 25 min). The solvent was evaporated, and the white solid 95 mg (78.7 %) was isolated. The pure product was dissolved in EtOH (10 mL) and HCl was added gradually. The temperature of the solution was kept at 5 °C throughout. HCl was added until the pH of the solution was 3. The reaction mixture was stirred for 5 min. The solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure. The desired product 7 was identified by 1H and ^{13}C NMR and by MS. Deuterium enrichment (>0.97 atom D per molecule) was determined from the mass spectrum.

4.2.1.1. *7-[2H]-tacrine hydrochloride (7)*. Yield: 86 mg (60 %); white solid; 1H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ 13.91 (s, 1H, HCl), 8.91 (bs, 1H, NH₂), 8.51 (s, 1H, Ar H-8), 8.06 (bs, 1H, NH₂), 7.91 (d, $J = 8.5$ Hz, 1H, Ar H-5), 7.83 (dd, $J = 8.5, 1.1$ Hz, 1H, Ar H-6), 2.97 (m, 2H, CH₂), 2.53 (m, 2H, CH₂), 1.84 (m, 4H, 2 \times CH₂) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (75.5 MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ 155.4, 151.3, 137.0, 132.8, 125.3 (deuterium triplet peak is missing), 123.2, 119.0, 114.7, 109.1, 27.7, 22.6, 21.0, 20.5 ppm. MS (ESI⁺) m/z 200 for $C_{13}H_{14}^2HN_2$ $[M+H]^+$. HR-ESI⁺ for $C_{13}H_{14}^2HN_2$ $[M+H]^+$ calculated 200.12925, found: 200.12931.

4.3. Lipophilicity, drug-plasma proteins binding, and phospholipids affinity assays

All measurements were performed using the protocols developed by Valko and co-workers [89,90] and implemented in our laboratory [90–92]. In brief, these methods offered determination of lipophilicity and affinity to phospholipids, expressed as Chromatographic Hydrophobicity Index (CHI) indices, and binding to plasma protein using a gradient elution experiment and comparison with reference substances.

Each chromatographic experiment was performed using the Prominence-1 LC-2030C 3D HPLC system controlled by the LabSolution software. During the investigation, three chromatographic columns with varying chemical modifications of their stationary phases were utilized.

- IAM.PC.DD2 (150 \times 4.6 mm \times 10.0 μ m with a guard column; Regis Technologies; USA);
- C₁₈ Hypersil GOLD™ (100 mm \times 4.6 mm; 5.0 μ m with a guard column; Thermo Scientific, USA);
- Chiralpak® HSA (50 \times 4 mm; 5 μ m with safety guard column; Daicel Chiral Technologies, USA)

All columns were equipped to guard columns with the same stationary phases as the main column. For Artificial Membrane Chromatography (IAM) and human serum albumin (HSA) affinity measurements, mobile phase A was a water solution of 50 mM ammonium acetate (VWR International, Leuven, Belgium) adjusted to physiological pH 7.4 with concentrated ammonia solution (Avantor Performance Materials Poland S.A., Gliwice, Poland). Chrom log D was determined in three pH solutions: 50 mM ammonium acetate water adjusted to pH 7.4 and 10.5 and acetic acid adjusted to 2.6. Ultrapure

water used for mobile phase preparation was obtained from a Milli-Q water purification system (Merck Millipore, Darmstadt, Germany) to a resistivity of 18.2 M Ω .

For phospholipid binding measurements, mobile phase B was HPLC grade acetonitrile (Chempur, Piekary Śląskie, Poland) with a linear gradient from 0 to 85 % B in 5.25 min and then held at 85 % ACN for 0.5 min. The flow rate of the mobile phase was 1.5 mL/min, and the IAM.PC.DD2 column was maintained at 30 °C.

For lipophilicity measurements, solvents and flow rate were the same as for IAM chromatography. The C₁₈ Hypersil GOLD™ column was maintained at 40 °C. Similarly, the linear gradient was applied from 0 to 5.25 min, but in this case, from 2 to 98 % CAN, and the maximum phase B concentration was maintained for 2.5 min.

For the determination of %HSA binding, HPLC grade isopropanol (VWR International, Leuven, Belgium) was used as mobile phase B. For the first 15 min, the linear gradient was applied from 0 to 20 % isopropanol and then held at 20 % isopropanol for 12 min. In the last 5 min of the sequence, the mobile phase mixture was changed back to pure ammonium acetate solution. The column temperature was maintained at 30 °C while the flow rate was 0.9 mL/min.

The reference substances used to calibrate the HSA, C₁₈ and IAM columns were purchased as follows: acetanilide, butyrophenone, diclofenac and octanophenone (Alfa Aesar, Haverhill, USA); acetophenone, benzimidazole, colchicine, indole, indometacin, paracetamol and theophylline (Sigma-Aldrich, Steinheim, Germany); nicardipine and nizatidine (Cayman Chemical, Michigan, USA); carbamazepine, heptanophenone, hexanophenone, propiophenone and valerophenone (Acros Organic, Pittsburg, USA).

The target solutes were dissolved in dimethyl sulfoxide (Avantor Performance Materials Poland S.A., Poland) to obtain a concentration of 200 μ g/mL. Detection was performed in the UV region at a wavelength of 190–300 nm. The injected volume was 5 μ L, each compound was analyzed in duplicate, and the difference between retention times was never more than 3 %. Retention times for the studied molecules and reference standards are summarized in the supplementary material, Tables S5 and S6.

Experimentally determined CHI values have been converted to chrom log *D* using the following equation [93]:

$$\text{Chrom log } D = 0.0525 \times \text{CHI} - 1.467 \quad (1)$$

In addition, the Property Forecast Index (PFI), the sum of the number of aromatic rings (#Ar), and a lipophilicity measure are used to reflect the principle of simultaneous minimisation of lipophilicity and aromaticity [94], which supports the selection of oral clinical candidates in GKS [95].

$$\text{PFI} = \text{Chrom log } D_{(7.4)} + \#\text{Ar} \quad (2)$$

In case of the HSA, the obtained result can be converted to a more informative percent of binding to (%HSA) using the following equations [89].

$$\% \text{HSA} = \frac{101 \times 10^{\log k_{\text{HSA}}}}{1 + 10^{\log k_{\text{HSA}}}} \quad (3)$$

4.4. Biological evaluation

4.4.1. In vitro inhibition studies on AChE and BChE

The hAChE/hBChE inhibitory activity of the tested derivatives was determined using Ellman's method [96–98] and is expressed as IC₅₀, i.e., the concentration that reduces the cholinesterase activity by 50 %. The human recombinant AChE and BChE were prepared at the Department of Toxicology and Military Pharmacy (Military Faculty of Medicine, Czech Republic) [99]. 5,5'-dithiobis(2-nitrobenzoic acid) (Ellman's reagent, DTNB), phosphate buffer (PB, pH 7.4), acetylthiocholine (ATC) and butyrylthiocholine (BTC), were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich,

Prague, Czech Republic. For measuring purposes – polystyrene Nunc 96-well microplates with flat bottom shape (ThermoFisher Scientific, USA) were utilized. Enzyme solutions were prepared at 2.0 units/mL in 2 mL aliquots. The assay medium consisted of 0.1 M PB (pH 7.4), 0.01 M DTNB, the enzyme, and 0.01 M substrate (ATC/BTC iodide solution). Tested compounds were added in the concentration range from 10 nM to 10 μ M and pre-incubated for 5 min. The reaction was started by the immediate addition of the substrate. The activity was determined by measuring the increase in absorbance at 412 for hAChE/hBChE at 37 °C at 2 min intervals - using a Multi-mode microplate reader Synergy 2 (Winooski, VT, USA). Each concentration was assayed in triplicate. Inhibition percentage and IC₅₀ were then calculated using Software GraphPad Prism 10 (San Diego, CA, USA).

4.4.2. Prediction of BBB permeability

The parallel artificial membrane permeability assay (PAMPA) has been used as the non-cell-based *in vitro* assay to predict BB penetration in a coated 96-well membrane filter [67]. The filter membrane of the donor plate was coated with PBL (Polar Brain Lipid, Avanti, USA) in dodecane (4 μ L of 20 mg/mL PBL in dodecane), and the acceptor well was filled with 300 μ L of PBS buffer (pH 7.4; V_A). Tested compounds were dissolved first in DMSO and then diluted with PBS (pH 7.4) to achieve the final concentration of 25–100 μ M in the donor well. The concentration of DMSO did not exceed 0.5 % (v/v) in the donor solution. 300 μ L of the donor solution (V_D) was added to the donor wells, and the donor filter plate was carefully put on the acceptor plate so that coated membrane was “in touch” with both the donor solution and acceptor buffer. The test compound diffused from the donor well through the polar brain lipid membrane (Area = 0.28 cm²) to the acceptor well. The concentration of the tested compound in both the donor and acceptor wells was assessed after 3, 4, 5, and 6 h of incubation, respectively, in quadruplicate using a UV plate reader Spark (Tecan Group Ltd, Männedorf, Switzerland) at the maximum absorption wavelength of each compound. Also prepared were solutions at the theoretical equilibrium of the given compound (i.e., the theoretical concentration if the donor and acceptor compartment were combined). The concentration of the compounds in the donor and acceptor well and the equilibrium concentration were calculated from the standard curve and expressed as the permeability (*Pe*) according to equation (4):

$$Pe = C \times -\ln \left(1 - \frac{[\text{drug}]_{\text{acceptor}}}{[\text{drug}]_{\text{equilibrium}}} \right),$$

where (4)

$$C = \left(\frac{V_D \times V_A}{(V_D + V_A) \times \text{Area} \times \text{Time}} \right).$$

4.4.3. Cytotoxicity assay

The cytotoxic profile of tested compounds was evaluated using human-origin cell lines HepG2. The cells were cultivated in Dublecco's modified Eagle's medium (DMEM, Biosera, Nuaille, France) supplemented with 10 % fetal bovine serum (FBS, Biosera), 1 % penicillin (10,000 U/mL)–streptomycin (10,000 μ g/mL) antibiotic solution (Merck, Germany) at 37 °C in CO₂ incubator (Binder CO₂ Incubator CB160, Tuttlingen, Germany) and routinely passaged by trypsinization at 75–85 % confluence.

The MTT (3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyl-tetrazolium bromide (Merck) reduction assay was used for measurement of compounds cytotoxicity. Cell viability was detected after 24 h incubation with the tested substances. For the assay, HepG2 cells were seeded into 96-well plates in 100 μ L volume and density of 15 \times 10³ cells per well. Cells were allowed to attach overnight before the treatment. The stock solutions of tested compounds were prepared in DMSO (Merck), which were further serially diluted in the appropriate culture medium and added to the cells in a 96-well culture plate. The final concentration of

DMSO did not exceed 1 % (v/v).

After 24 h incubation, the medium containing serially diluted substances was aspirated from each well and replaced by 100 μ L of fresh medium containing MTT (0.5 mg/mL). Plates were subsequently incubated at 37 °C in a CO₂ incubator for 1 h. Thereafter, the medium was aspirated, and purple crystals of MTT formazan were dissolved in 100 μ L DMSO under shaking. The optical density of each well was measured using Spark® multimode microplate reader (Tecan Group Ltd., Männedorf, Switzerland) at 570 nm.

The cytotoxicity of tested compounds was expressed as value IC₅₀, which was calculated using 4-parametric nonlinear regression with statistic software GraphPad Prism (version 9.3.0 for Windows, GraphPad Software Inc., USA). Data were obtained from at least four independent experiments performed in triplicates. The IC₅₀ value was expressed as mean \pm SEM.

4.4.4. Microsomal stability determination

4.4.4.1. Human liver microsomes incubation. The tested compounds **5a**, **5e**, **5i**, **5m**, and **7** were incubated with Human Liver Microsomes (HLM), according to Finger et al. [100] Briefly, 5 μ L of DMSO stock solution was mixed with 12.5 μ L of pooled Human Liver Microsomes (concentration 0,5 mg/mL, H2620, LOT no. 1210347, SekiSui, XenoTech, Canada) and 458 μ L of 0,1 M potassium phosphate buffer solution (pH = 7,4) and preincubated for 5 min (300 RPM, 25 °C). The concentration of incubated compounds was set at 3 μ M. The biotransformation reaction was started by the addition of 25 μ L of RapidStart NADPH Regenerating System (K5000, LOT. 1910008, SekiSui, XenoTech, Canada) and then incubated for 5 different time points (0, 5, 15, 30, 45 min). The reaction was terminated by the addition of 500 μ L of cooled acetonitrile (−20 °C) with 1 μ M internal standard IS; compound [100] and centrifuged for 5 min (14 000 RPM, 20 °C). Subsequently, 400 μ L of supernatant was transferred to the vial and analyzed by LC-MS.

4.4.4.2. LC-MS analysis. The LC-MS analysis of the incubated samples was performed using the same system as described in the General Methods and Chemistry section. The chosen analytical conditions are based on the method that has already been published for identifying THA derivative metabolites [42]. Briefly, a reverse-phase Kinetex 1.7 μ m PFP column (100 \times 2.1 mm; Phenomenex, Torrance, CA, USA) was used as a stationary phase, and purified water with 0.1 % formic acid (mobile phase A) and LC-MS grade acetonitrile with 0.1 % formic acid (mobile phase B) were used as the mobile phases. The method started with 2 % B for 1 min, then the gradient gradually switched to 30 % B in the eighth min, after that switched to 100 % B in the ninth min, remained at 100 % B for 1 min, and then went back to 2 % B with equilibration for 3.5 min. The total run time of the method was 13.5 min. The column temperature was kept constant at 40 °C, the flow of the mobile phase was 0.5 mL/min, and the injection volume was 5 μ L. The peak areas of the compounds (Acmp) and internal standards (AIS) were detected in extracted ion chromatograms from the mass spectrometer data in positive mode. The Acmp/AIS was calculated and logarithmized. From a plot of ln Acmp/AIS against the incubation time, the gradient (k value) was established. The t_{1/2} value and CL_{int} were calculated according to the Cyprotex protocol [101] and compared with known fast and slow metabolically degraded standards of verapamil and diazepam (Table 6). The identification of 7-OH-THA metabolite was confirmed by the retention time and HRMS spectrum of 7-OH-THA chemical standard. The amount of 7-OH-THA formed was expressed as peak area and related in % to 7-OH-THA peak area gained from THA HLM incubation.

4.4.5. Evaluation of antagonist activity at NMDAR

Human embryonic kidney 293 (HEK293) cells were cultured in Opti-MEM I media supplemented with 5 % fetal bovine serum (FBS; v/v; Thermo Fisher Scientific). Subsequent transfections were carried out in

Opti-MEM I media, utilizing 0.9 μ L of MATra-A Reagent (IBA) and 900 ng of DNA vectors containing the human versions of the GluN1-1a and GluN2B subunits along with green fluorescent protein (GFP, pQBI, Takara). Following transfection, the cells were put on the magnet for 30 min. Then, HEK293 cells were trypsinized, cultivated in Opti-MEM I with 1 % FBS, 2 mM MgCl₂, and 3 mM kynurenic acid on glass coverslips, and subjected to electrophysiological recordings within 24–48 h [102].

Electrophysiological recordings were executed at room temperature using an Axopatch 200B amplifier (Molecular Devices). A holding potential of −60 mV and +40 mV was employed for voltage-clamp recordings, with 80 % series resistance (<10 M Ω) and capacitance (80 %) compensation. Current responses were filtered at 2 kHz using an eight-pole Bessel low-pass filter, digitized at 5 kHz, and recorded through pClamp 10 software (Molecular Devices). Glass pipettes, with tip resistance ranging from 3 to 6 M Ω , were fashioned with a micropipette puller model P-1000 (Sutter Instrument Co.) and loaded with an intracellular recording solution consisted of (in mM): 125 gluconic acid, 15 CsCl, 5 BAPTA, 10 HEPES, 3 MgCl₂, 0.5 CaCl₂, and 2 ATP-Mg salts (pH adjusted to 7.2 with CsOH). The extracellular recording solution (ECS) included (in mM) 160 NaCl, 2.5 KCl, 10 HEPES, 10 glucose, 0.2 EDTA, and 0.7 CaCl₂ (pH adjusted to 7.3 with NaOH). A microprocessor-controlled multi-barrel rapid perfusion system enabled the solution application, including the saturating concentrations of the agonist L-glutamate (1 mM) and co-agonist glycine (100 μ M). Compounds, prepared as 10 mM stock solutions freshly before each experiment in DMSO, were employed to obtain concentration-response curves utilizing Equation (1): $I = 1 / (1 + ([\text{compound}] / IC_{50})^h)$, where IC₅₀ represents the concentration causing 50 % inhibition, [compound] is the compound concentration, and h is the apparent Hill coefficient. The DMSO concentration did not exceed 1 % in the applied ECS, and all chemicals for recording solutions were procured from Merck [85].

4.4.6. Assessment of dehydrogenase activity and glutathione levels in neuronal cells

4.4.6.1. Cell culture and treatment. The neuroblastoma cell line SH-SY5Y was purchased from the American Type Culture Collection (ATCC No. CRL-2266, Manassas, VA, USA). The cells were cultured in Dulbecco's Modified Eagle's medium (DMEM/F12 = 1:1) supplemented with 15 % (v/v) fetal bovine serum (Gibco, USA), 2 mM L-glutamin (Gibco), 1 % non-essential amino acids (Gibco) and 50 μ g/mL penicillin-streptomycin solution (Gibco) and incubated at 37 °C in 5 % CO₂.

The SH-SY5Y cells were seeded in 100 μ L of cell culture medium in a 96-well plates at density of 2×10^4 . The cells were seeded for 24 h and then exposed to **5i**, **5m**, THA, and 7-PhO-THA for 6, 24 and 48 h. The stock solutions of tested compounds were prepared in 100 % DMSO (Merck, USA) and then were diluted in the culture medium to obtain the final concentrations of 0–100 μ M. Non-treated cells were used as a negative control.

4.4.6.2. Glutathione assay. The glutathione (GSH) levels were measured using an optimized monochlorobimane assay [103]. The working solution of monochlorobimane (MCB, Merck, USA) was freshly prepared at the time of analysis by dilution in DPBS (pH 7; 1 mM, Merck, USA) and tempered at 37 °C for 30 min. After treating cells with the tested compounds, 20 μ L of MCB solution was added to the cells in 96-well plates, and the measurement started immediately (the final concentration of MCB in a well was 40 μ M). The fluorescence intensity (Ex/Em = 394/490 nm) was measured for 10 min using a SPARK microplate reader (Tecan, Austria). The fluorescence was expressed as the slope of a fluorescence change over time. The GSH levels were expressed as the percentage relative to GSH levels in untreated cells (control = 100 %). In addition, we evaluated the occurrence of interference of tested compounds with the GSH assays. The maximal background fluorescence

observed in blank samples containing tested compounds was always lower than 5 % of the signal in untreated cells.

4.4.6.3. ATP assay. The quantification of intracellular ATP levels was detected using a luciferase luminescence assay. After the treatment, the culture medium was replaced with 70 μL of cold 1 % Triton-X-100 for cell lysis, incubated for 10 min, and centrifuged ($4800\times g$; 5 min; 4 $^{\circ}\text{C}$). To detect intracellular ATP concentration, 90 μL of reaction solution was added to 10 μL of a lysate. The reaction solution included 20 \times reaction buffer (500 mM Tricine buffer, pH 7.8; 10 mM MgSO_4), 5 mg/mL luciferase, 10 mM D-luciferin, 0.1 M DTT, and distilled water. Luminescence measurement was performed at $\text{Em} = 560 \text{ nm}$ using a SPARK microplate reader (Tecan, Austria). The intracellular ATP levels were expressed as the percentage of ATP levels related to that in control cells (control = 100 %).

4.4.6.4. Dehydrogenase activity assay. Dehydrogenase activity was evaluated by the resazurin assay. The resazurin assay measures the activity of intra- and extramitochondrial dehydrogenases. The working solution of resazurin (Merck, USA) was prepared by dilution in DPBS 1 \times (pH 7; 1 mM, Merck, USA) to the concentration of 0.3 mg/mL. After cell treatment, 20 μL of resazurin solution was added to the cells in 96-well plates, and the measurement started immediately. The fluorescence intensity ($\text{Ex}/\text{Em} = 530/590 \text{ nm}$) was measured for 20 min using a SPARK microplate reader (Tecan, Austria) while incubating at 37 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. The dehydrogenase activity was expressed as the percentage of total cellular dehydrogenase activity relative to that in control cells (control = 100 %). At the tested concentrations, no significant interference of the tested compounds was observed with any of the assays.

4.4.6.5. Fluorescence microscopy. Phalloidin-FITC (Thermo Fisher, USA) staining of actin filaments followed by Hoechst 33258 (1 mg/mL; Merck, USA) staining of cell nuclei was performed in SH-SY5Y cells. Cells were cultured in 200 μL of cell culture medium on cell culture chamber slides at a density of 2×10^4 cells per well. After seeding, the culture medium was replaced by 200 μL of tested solutions, and the cells were treated for 6–48 h. The cells were fixed with 3.7 % formaldehyde for 5 min at 37 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. The cells were permeabilized with 0.1 % Triton X-100 for 15 min at 37 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Then, phalloidin-FITC (1 μM) was incubated with the cells for 30 min at 37 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ to visualize actin filaments. Hoechst 33258 was used to visualize cell nuclei at a final solution of 2 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$. After 10 min of incubation, the cells were washed two times with Dulbecco's phosphate buffer (DPBS; pH 7; 1 mM). The actin filaments (FITC filter, 480/30 nm) and cell nuclei (DAPI filter, 375/28 nm) were visualized with an Eclipse 80i fluorescence microscope (Nikon, Japan).

4.4.6.6. Statistical evaluation. All spectrometric measurements were performed in multiplets ($n = 3-6$) in at least three independent experiments. Statistical analysis was performed using OriginPro 9.0.0 (OriginLab, USA). Statistical significance was analyzed after normality testing using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by the Bonferroni posttest to compare the results with negative controls at significance level of $p = 0.05$. At the tested concentrations, no significant interference of tested compounds with any of the used assays was observed.

4.5. In vivo pharmacokinetic study

4.5.1. Animals

Young adult Balb/c male mice weighing 25–30 g were purchased from Velaz (Únětice, Czech Republic). They were kept in an air-conditioned enclosure with light from 07:00 a.m. to 7:00 p.m. and were allowed access to standard food (Cerea Corporation, Pardubice, Czech Republic) and tap water *ad libitum*. Vivarium accreditation number no. 69233/2015-MZE-17214; Military Faculty of Medicine,

University of Defence.

The animals were acclimatized for at least ten days before starting the experiments. The mice were divided into groups of 4 animals. The saline solution with the experimental compound was prepared and used immediately for testing without further storage.

The experimental animals were handled under the supervision of the Ethics Committee of the Military Faculty of Medicine, University of Defence, Czech Republic (No. MO-474807/2024-1457). All *in vivo* studies were performed following ethical guidelines.

4.5.2. Short study of safety, absorption, and brain distribution in mice

4.5.2.1. Design of in vivo experiments. The short safety study of the new candidate consists of toxicity signs observation, macroscopic examination, and organ histopathology.

Mice were randomly assigned to the experimental groups of four males. **5m** and the sham-treated group were administered intraperitoneally (i.p., 10 % kolliphor in saline with 5 % DMSO). Based on maximal solubility, two doses were selected: 10 mg/kg (0.1 mL/10 g of animal weight) and 15 mg/kg (0.15 mL/10 g of animal weight). Based on our experience, we perceive the combination of administration routine, the vehicle, and the maximum volumes as safe for the selected animal model.

Following administration, animals were observed for signs of toxicity, such as cardiovascular, respiratory, or nervous system changes. Weight loss, or reduced food consumption, has been recorded. According to the FELASA classification, these were assessed in the first 2 h and then periodically for 48 h. The classification of toxicity signs and subsequent determination of the MTD, or NOAEL were performed following previous studies [104,105]. All animals surviving for 48 h were euthanized by isoflurane and subjected to basic macroscopic necropsy and histopathological examination.

Liver and kidney samples were collected for standard histopathologic examination. Organs were fixed with 10 % neutral-buffered formalin (Bamed, Ceske Budejovice, Czech Republic), histologically processed, and stained with hematoxylin and eosin (both Merck), according to Pejchal et al. [106]. Histopathological changes were evaluated using a BX-51 microscope (Olympus, Tokyo, Japan).

Based on short safety study results, the dose selected for the absorption and brain distribution study was 15 mg/kg. After the i.p. administration (0.15 mL/10 g of animal weight; 10 % kolliphor in saline with 5 % DMSO), blood samples were collected from mice under deep terminal anesthesia (Isoflurane, Vetpharma Animal Health, Barcelona, Spain; 96/026/DC/16-S) directly by cardiac puncture into heparinized 1.5 mL tubes at selected time intervals: 15, 30, 60, and 120 min; $n = 4$). The blood samples were centrifuged at $5000\times g$ for 8 min (4 $^{\circ}\text{C}$), and the plasmas were stored at $-80 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ until the HPLC analysis.

The blood in brain vessels would interfere with the assay of proper brain tissue concentrations. Therefore, the animals were perfused transcardially with saline solution (0.9 % NaCl) for 5 min (5 mL/min). After perfusion, the skull was opened, and the brain was carefully removed and immediately stored at $-80 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ until the HPLC analysis.

All treated animals in the pharmacokinetic study were also intensively observed during the experiment for signs of toxicity, such as respiratory, cardiovascular, and nervous system disability.

4.5.3. Pharmacokinetic study - HPLC-MS analysis

The brains were weighed and PBS (from tablets, Sigma-Aldrich, Steinheim, Germany) was added four times their weight. Then the brains were homogenised by T-25 Ultra Turrax disperser (IKA, Staufen, Germany). This homogenate was transferred to a microcentrifuge tube, sonicated by UP 50H needle homogenizer (Hielscher, Teltow, Germany), and the final homogenate was stored at $-80 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ prior to extraction.

190 μL of brain homogenate or 95 μL of plasma was spiked with 10 μL of internal standard (IS; 2 dC described by Gorecki et al. [107], in

Table 9

Chromatographic and mass spectrometric characteristics of internal standard and compound **5m** used in pharmacokinetic assessment.

Compound	R _t	Mass searched (<i>m/z</i>)
5m	3	295.120–295.130
2 dC (IS)	3.8	534.150–534.160

R_t, retention time; *m/z*, mass to charge ratio; IS, internal standard.

methanol) for brain homogenate, 5 µl for plasmatic samples, with the final concentration being 100 nM, then the sample was vortexed and 100 µl of 1 M sodium hydroxide (brain homogenate) or 50 µl (plasma) and 700 µl of ethylacetate (ACS reagent, VWR chemicals, Fontenay-sous-Bois, France) for brain homogenate or 350 µl for plasma was added. The samples were then shaken for 10 min (1800 RPM, VM-10 orbital motion Vortex Mixer, witeg Labortechnik GmbH, Wertheim, Germany) and centrifuged (15610×g, 5 min, Universal 320 R centrifuge, Hettich, Tuttlingen, Germany). 500 µl (brain homogenate) or 250 (plasma) µl of supernatant was transferred to a microtube and evaporated in a CentriVap concentrator to dryness (Labconco Corporation, Kansas City, USA). Prior to the analysis, the samples were reconstituted in 100 µl of 50 % (v/v) ACN. Calibration samples were prepared by spiking 180 µl of blank brain homogenate or 90 µl of plasma with 10 µl for homogenate or 5 µl for plasma of analyte (compound **5m**) methanol solution (final concentrations range from 1 nM to 10 µM) and 10 (5) µl of IS (final concentration 100 nM) and then were vortexed and extracted as above.

To determine the concentration of compound **5m** in plasma and brain homogenate HPLC-MS analysis was performed. The system used in this study was Dionex Ultimate 3000 UHPLC: RS LPG quaternary pump, RS column compartment, RS autosampler, diode array detector, Chromleon software (version 7.2.9 build 11323, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Germering, Germany) with a Q Exactive Plus Orbitrap mass spectrometer with Thermo Xcalibur software (version 4.3.73.11, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Bremen, Germany). Detection was carried out by mass spectrometry in positive mode. Settings of the heated electrospray source were: spray voltage 3.5 kV, capillary temperature: 262 °C, sheath gas: 50 arbitrary units, auxiliary gas: 12.5 arbitrary units, spare gas: 2.5 arbitrary units, probe heater temperature: 300 °C, max spray current: 100 µA, S-lens RF level: 50.

Data were obtained by reverse phase gradient elution method with a C18 column (Kinetex EVO C18 2.1 × 50 mm, 1.7 µm, Phenomenex, Torrance, California, USA) with mobile phase A: 0.1 % (v/v) formic acid in ultrapure water of ASTM type I (resistance 18.2 MΩ cm at 25 °C) prepared by Barnstead Smart2Pure 3 UV/UF apparatus (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Bremen, Germany) and mobile phase B: 0.1 % (v/v) formic acid in LC-MS grade acetonitrile. The flow was constant at 0.4 ml/min. The method started with 0.3 min of the isocratic flow of 5 % B, then the gradient of B rose to 100 % B in 3 min and remained constant at 100 % B for 0.7 min. Then, the composition went back to 5 % B and equilibrated for 3.5 min. The total run time was 7.5 min. The column was tempered to 27 °C. The injection volume was 5 µL.

The concentration of compounds was measured by a mass spectrometer in positive mode, operating in total ion current mode. Retention time and searched masses are in Table 9.

The calibration curve for plasmatic and brain homogenate levels of **5m** had 9 points ranging from 1 nM to 10 µM.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Barbora Svobodova: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Zuzana Moravcova**: Investigation. **Anna Misiachna**: Investigation. **Gabriela Novakova**: Investigation. **Ales Marek**: Methodology, Investigation. **Vladimir Finger**: Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation. **Jitka Odvarkova**: Investigation. **Jaroslav Pejchal**: Writing –

review & editing, Methodology. **Jana Zdarova Karasova**: Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation. **Jakub Netolicky**: Investigation. **Marek Ladislav**: Investigation. **Martina Hrabanova**: Methodology, Investigation. **Ales Sorf**: Methodology, Investigation. **Lubica Muckova**: Methodology, Investigation. **Lenka Fikejzlova**: Methodology, Investigation. **Marketa Benkova**: Methodology, Investigation. **Martin Novak**: Methodology, Investigation. **Lukas Prchal**: Methodology, Investigation. **Jan Capek**: Methodology, Investigation. **Jiri Handl**: Methodology, Investigation. **Tomas Rousar**: Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition. **Katarzyna Ewa Greber**: Methodology, Investigation. **Krzysztof Ciura**: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation. **Martin Horak**: Writing – original draft, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation. **Ondrej Soukup**: Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Jan Korabecny**: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work, the author(s) used ChatGPT 4o to correct and improve level of English. After using ChatGPT 4o, the author(s) reviewed and edited the content as needed and take(s) full responsibility for the content of the published article.

Funding

The study was supported by the Czech Academy of Sciences, Grant/Award Number: RVO 61388963; by the Ministry of Defence of the Czech Republic “Long Term Organization Development Plan 1011” – Healthcare Challenges of WMD II of the Military Faculty of Medicine Hradec Kralove, University of Defence, Czech Republic (Project No: DZRO-FVZ22-ZHN II); by Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports of the Czech Republic (Project No. SV/FVZ202303); by The National Science Centre of Poland (Project No. 2022/47/D/NZ7/01043); by the Czech Science Foundation (Project No. 23-07570S); and by the Biomedical Indicators for Personalized Medicine project (BIPOLE), project ID CZ.02.01.01/00/23_021/0008439, co-funded by the European Union.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgement

MarvinSketch software, version [24.3.0], developed by ChemAxon (Budapest, Hungary) was used for drawing, displaying and characterizing chemical structures, substructures and reactions. The authors are grateful to Iveta Kaderavkova for animal handling.

Abbreviations:

AChE – acetylcholinesterase; AD – Alzheimer’s disease; ADMET – absorption, distribution, metabolism, excretion, toxicity; BBB – blood-brain barrier; BChE – butyrylcholinesterase; ChEs – cholinesterases; CNS – central nervous system; GSH – glutathione; LC-MS – liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry; MS – mass spectra; MTDLs – multi-target directed ligands; MTT – 3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide; NOAEL – no observed adverse effect level; NMDAR – N-methyl-D-aspartate receptor; PAINS – pan-assay

interference compounds; PAMPA – parallel artificial membrane permeability assay; PBS – phosphate-buffered saline; PK – pharmacokinetics; SH-SY5Y – human neuroblastoma cell line; THA – tacrine; UHPLC – ultra-high performance liquid chromatography; 7-MEOTA – 7-methoxytacrine; 7-PhO-THA – 7-phenoxytacrine.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejmech.2025.117678>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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